

Redundant parallel beam multi-axis force sensor – Multi-beam structure

Hongwen Ma, and Yuzhuo Xing

Abstract—A method to design a high stiffness and low crosstalk (cross coupling, dimensional coupling, class II error) multi-axis force sensor (MAFS) is proposed in this paper. The characteristic of the sensor designed using this method is a parallel structure of multiple strain beams between two rigid platforms. The main aspect of this method is the space transformation of forces and deformations between the global coordinate system and the local coordinate system based on elastic mechanics and theoretical mechanics. The stiffness of such a structure is considerable, the forces imposed on the sensor can be easily and quickly calculated using a linear equation system. The calculation method of a multi-beam-structure MAFS is derived in this paper. The calculated results theoretically have nearly no crosstalk and verified by finite element simulations. The study shows that a redundant parallel beam structure between two rigid platforms can be considered an ideal linear elastic system, and it can be calculated under simple conditions where some local forces (local strains) can be observed.

Key words—Crosstalk, Finite element analysis, Linear elastic system, Multi-axis force sensor, Redundant parallel beam

Notation: Symbol of space vector

Coordinate system: i - Local coordinate system $x_i y_i z_i$;
 g - Global coordinate system $xy z$;

Beam number: i ; g or blank indicates the global force or displacement imposed on the loading platform;

Space vector: Q - Generalized force including both the force and the torque; F - Force; M - Torque;
 Δ - Generalized deformation including both the displacement and the rotation; ΔD - Displacement deformation; $\Delta \theta$ - Rotation deformation;
 r - Displacement of the beam; β - Rotation of the beam;

Vector direction: x - Along/About axis x ; y - Along/About axis y ;
 z - Along/About axis z ; Blank indicates a vector include x , y and z ;

Point the vector imposed on: o - Origin of the global coordinate system $xy z$; o_i - Origin of the local coordinate system $x_i y_i z_i$;

I. INTRODUCTION

MAFS is one of the most important sensors [1-2] for robotics, aerospace[3-5], bionics[6-9], marine engineering[10], medical equipment[6, 11-13], machining processes [14], wind/water tunnel balance [15-17], rocket/water jet engine thrust testing [10, 18], stir welding [19] and automobile testing [20].

According to the measurement axis, a MAFS can be classified into a planar 3-axis force/torque sensor (forces along the x and y axes and torque about the z axis) [21], a 3-axis force sensor (forces along the x , y , and z axes) [22-25], a 6-axis force

sensor, and other force sensors (2, 4, and 5 axes)[26-27]. The 6-axis force sensor is the most general sensor.

According to the structure of the sensor, MAFS can be classified into an integrated elastic structure, the Stewart parallel structure, a piezoelectric crystal structure, a micro structure, a frictionless guideway structure, a flexible structure and other structures [22, 28]. The integrated elastic structure comprises various structures such as a three vertical-rib integrated type developed by Watson et al.[29], an I-beams and interconnecting blocks type developed by Folchi [30], a double ring type developed by Schott [31], the Maltese cross type [32-35], which is currently the most popular structure in commercial products, a 3-beam nonradial symmetry type developed by Hu [36], an eight vertical beams type developed by Chen [37], an E-type structure [38], a cross-shaped type [39-40], a T-shaped bar [41], and an frame/truss type [42]. The Stewart parallel structure comprises mechanical hinge and flexure hinge types [43-50] where each structure is composed of 6 beams or 8 redundant beams. The piezoelectric crystal structure comprises 4-set [51] and 8-set types [52] along with a ring type [53], and all these sets or rings are placed in one plane. A micro MAFS or an acceleration sensor is manufactured by MEMS technology [7, 11, 24, 54-57]. The frictionless guideway structure comprises air-lubricated [58] and magnetic suspension types [59]. The size and weight of such structures are considerable, which means that such structures are suitable for a calibration equipment. The flexible structure [60-61] is usually used in force feedback soft fingers, although the accuracy of such a sensor is low, its impact resistance is strong.

According to sensitive measurement components, a MAFS can be classified into a strain gage type (resistance, semiconductor, FBG, piezoresistance), a piezoelectric crystal type, an optical type [23, 62-63], and an electrical type (capacitance, inductance, hall) [7, 61, 64-65]. Usually, the strain gage sensor, optical sensor, and electrical sensor are mainly used in integrated elastic structure MAFSs. Strain gage and piezoelectric crystal structures are mainly used in Stewart parallel structure MAFSs, and a single direction crystal is usually used to measure the force along the beam. Multiple sets of piezoelectric crystals are used in piezoelectric crystal structure MAFSs, and all of the crystal sets are placed in one plane. Each set of piezoelectric crystals is used to measure

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forces in different directions, which comprises yx crystals (with shear effect), yx crystals, and xy crystals (with compression effect). Piezoresistance, piezoelectric oxide semiconductors, and capacitance are mainly used in microstructure MAFSs. The Hall sensor is usually used in force feedback soft fingers with a flexible structure.

Most integrated elastic structure MAFSs are decoupled using a decoupling matrix. This was first proposed by Scheiman [66] and revised by Shimano [67], Li [68], and Huang [69]. It is still widely used. The principle of minimum energy is used in this method, and all the sensitive deformations are considered to be in linear relationships with the measured forces. The decoupling matrix is obtained by calibration experiments or through finite element calculations. This method is dependent on the assumed linear relationship between sensitive deformations and measured forces. However, this assumption is not accurate in most cases. Screw theory is used to calculate Stewart structure MAFSs [2]. The assumption is made that all the hinges in the platform are ideal hinges without any frictional force. A flexure hinge used in some Stewart MAFSs [70-72]. Although almost no frictional force exists in the flexure hinge, the elastic torque in the flexure hinge omitted in the calculation will affect the results. The flexure hinge should be very thin to minimize the elastic torque, and the loading capacity of the MAFS should be small. Piezoelectric crystal MAFSs are calculated in a simple manner using simple theory mechanics where each set of crystals is considered an ideal 3-axis force sensor measured from an ideal point, and the non-uniform deformation of the crystals is ignored. For all of these methods, the crosstalk of MAFSs currently used is large (usually 2% to ~5%). The stiffness of the mechanical hinge Stewart type and the piezoelectric crystal type MAFSs is relatively large. Because the stiffness of most the other MAFSs is relatively low, a safety structure to prevent a large deformation of the structure or adopting a rubber structure to decrease the vibration of the structure is recommended [73].

To improve the accuracy of MAFSs, many correction methods have been proposed such as maximum likelihood [74], least square support vector machine [51, 75], objective-optimization of MAFS compliance matrix [9], and genetic algorithm [76]. These methods can significantly improve the accuracy of a MAFS, however it is difficult to acquire enough accurate test data for a MAFS, and the test data will be variable (temperature, component aging) with time, making repeated calibrations difficult. In addition, the calculation speed is slow, indicating that a real time calculation is difficult.

Recently, redundant elastic mechanics were applied to MAFS. The decoupling method for a redundant-parallel-beam structure is proposed by Zhao in [2]. The 8-set planar layout of piezoelectric crystals were used to establish such a sensor, and the combined elastic deformation of each set of piezoelectric crystal was considered in the calculation formula by Liu [52]. There are 8 beams utilized in this Stewart sensor, and the concerted elastic deformation of each beam was considered in the calculation formulas by Zhao [2, 45]. An over-constrained 6-dimensional force sensor based on a parallel mechanism of steel ball structures was proposed by Niu [77]. The relationship

between the deformations and forces is considered to be a 1-dimensional geometric relationship, which is introduced in the decoupling matrix or within screw theory. These methods are of great significance in revealing the nature of force coupling which point out a direction to further analyze the complex relationship between the force and deformation.

For some space unit measurements, like the posture of a rigid body, the accuracy can be easily over 1% full scale, considering both uniaxial accuracy and crosstalk. The accuracy of a uniaxial force sensor can also be easily over 1% full scale. Therefore, all of these sensors can be widely applicable to many other fields.

The main commercial manufacturers of MAFSs are ATI, Schunk, AMTI, Kistler, JR3, HBM, BOTTA Systems, Weiss Robotics, Interface, Sunrise Instruments, ME, Optoforce (Merged with Onrobot), Hypersen, Nanjing Bio-Inspired, Changzhou Right, A&D Technology (wheel force sensors), Bioforcen, Forsentek (3-dimensional), Bertec, Kunweitech, and MinebeaMitsumi (3-dimensional). Maltese cross MAFSs are utilized by most of these companies, and the typical crosstalk for these commercial sensors is between 2%~5%. They are mainly utilized commercially in situations where the multi-axis force measurements do not need to be very accurate. Such applications include assembly, grinding, polishing, vehicle crash tests, and wheel force tests. In applications where higher accuracy of multi-axis force measurements is needed, multiple uniaxial force sensors are utilized to replace a MAFS, such as LBR iiwa from KUKA designed at DLR in Germany [78]. One uniaxial torque sensor is used in each joint of the robot. The robot is effective and widely applied, however, this alternative method has the usual shortcoming of a more complex structure, higher price, oversized dimensions, and a large inertial force. In spite of haptic/force feedback is utilized by many minimally-invasive surgeries robotics [79-83] in academic research, the commercial MIS robot, Da Vinci, is based only on visual feedback because of the inaccuracy and unreliability of the 6-axis force sensor.

Fig. 1. Structures of redundant parallel beam MAFS

Conventional MAFSs have the advantage of low cost, simple structure and easy application. Therefore, they are widely used

in various fields. However, because of the inaccuracy of the mechanical/mathematics models and/or the unpredictable frictional forces, the crosstalk is relatively high. Therefore, a strictly decoupling structure and an accurate calculation method are needed.

Obviously, the stiffness of structures (Fig. 1) is high enough, and there are no frictional forces. All of the structures consist of multiple, simple parallel strain beams. However, the questions are 1) could such structures be calculated as MAFSSs?; 2) would the calculation results have high enough accuracy for use in applications?; and 3) could the calculation become fast enough?

II. ANALYSIS OF AN ELASTOMER

Fig. 2. Elastomer connected with a rigid body

Various elastomers can be used in MAFSSs as shown in Fig. 2. A simple uniform strain beam is used as an example to analyze the MAFSS.

Fig. 3. Simplification of the contact force between a rigid platform and a strain beam

According to Saint Venant's principle, all forces on the strain beam are simplified to six concentrated forces imposed on the center of the contact line between the strain beam and the loading platform, as shown in Fig. 3. Usually Euler-Bernoulli, Timoshenko, and other modern high order beam theories can be used to analyze the strain beam [33]. To simplify analysis, Euler-Bernoulli beam theory is used in this paper.

Fig. 4. Forces and deformations in the local coordinate system, based on Euler-Bernoulli beam theory.

Because the deformation of the beam is extremely small and the material works within the elastic range, the deformation of the beam presents a linear relationship with the load. Unlike the conventional complex integrated elastic structures, the linear

relationship between the deformation and the load in a simple cantilever beam can be considered accurate, especially where the deformation is dramatically small. The superposition method can be used to calculate the deformations of the beam. The deformations of a strain beam are shown in Fig. 4.

In the local coordinate system $x_i y_i z_i$,

$${}^i \Delta D_x^i = \frac{{}^i F_x^i l^i}{EA^i}, \quad (1)$$

$${}^i \Delta D_y^i = {}^i \Delta D_{M_y}^i + {}^i \Delta D_{F_y}^i = \frac{{}^i M_y^i (l^i)^2}{2EI_z^i} + \frac{{}^i F_y^i (l^i)^3}{3EI_z^i} + \frac{{}^i F_y^i l^i}{GA^i}, \quad (2)$$

$${}^i \Delta D_z^i = {}^i \Delta D_{M_z}^i + {}^i \Delta D_{F_z}^i = \frac{{}^i M_z^i (l^i)^2}{2EI_y^i} + \frac{{}^i F_z^i (l^i)^3}{3EI_y^i} + \frac{{}^i F_z^i l^i}{GA^i}, \quad (3)$$

$${}^i \Delta \theta_x^i = \frac{{}^i M_x^i l^i}{GI_x^i}, \quad (4)$$

$${}^i \Delta \theta_y^i = {}^i \Delta \theta_{M_y}^i + {}^i \Delta \theta_{F_y}^i = \frac{{}^i M_y^i l^i}{EI_y^i} + \frac{{}^i F_y^i (l^i)^2}{2EI_y^i}, \quad (5)$$

$${}^i \Delta \theta_z^i = {}^i \Delta \theta_{M_z}^i + {}^i \Delta \theta_{F_z}^i = \frac{{}^i M_z^i l^i}{EI_z^i} + \frac{{}^i F_z^i (l^i)^2}{2EI_z^i}. \quad (6)$$

Where, E – Elasticity modulus; G – Shear modulus; A^i – Section area; l^i – Length of the beam; I_x^i, I_y^i, I_z^i – Moment of inertia about axes x_i, y_i , and z_i respectively;

III. ESTABLISHMENT OF A LOCAL COORDINATE SYSTEM

The beam's posture in the space can be expressed by methods such as vector method, Euler transformation method, pitch/yaw/roll method, to simplify the analysis, a coordinate transformation method is proposed, as shown in Fig. 5. It is obtained by the following steps:

Step 1: Rotate the beam by β_x^i about axis x ;

Step 2: Rotate the beam by β_y^i about axis y ;

Step 3: Rotate the beam by β_z^i about axis z ;

Step 4: Transfer the beam by $r^i (r_x^i, r_y^i, r_z^i)$ along x, y , and z axes.

Then, the transformation matrixes are:

$$Rot(x, \beta_x^i) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c\beta_x^i & -s\beta_x^i \\ 0 & s\beta_x^i & c\beta_x^i \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

$$Rot(y, \beta_y^i) = \begin{bmatrix} c\beta_y^i & 0 & s\beta_y^i \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -s\beta_y^i & 0 & c\beta_y^i \end{bmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

$$Rot(z, \beta_z^i) = \begin{bmatrix} c\beta_z^i & -s\beta_z^i & 0 \\ s\beta_z^i & c\beta_z^i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} Rot(x, y, z) &= Rot(z, \beta_z^i) Rot(y, \beta_y^i) Rot(x, \beta_x^i) \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} c\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i & -s\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i & s\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i \\ c\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i & c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i & -c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i \\ -s\beta_y^i & c\beta_y^i s\beta_x^i & c\beta_y^i c\beta_x^i \end{bmatrix}, \text{ and (10)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} Rot^T(x, y, z) &= Rot^T(x, \Delta\beta_x^i) Rot^T(y, \Delta\beta_y^i) Rot^T(z, \Delta\beta_z^i) \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} c\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i & c\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i & -s\beta_y^i \\ -s\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i & c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i & c\beta_y^i s\beta_x^i \\ s\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i & -c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i & c\beta_y^i c\beta_x^i \end{bmatrix}. \text{ (11)} \end{aligned}$$

Where $s\beta = \sin(\beta)$, $c\beta = \cos(\beta)$.

Fig. 5. Establishment of a local coordinate system and the relationship of the local coordinate system with the global coordinate system

IV. DEFORMATION TRANSFORMATION BETWEEN THE GLOBAL AND THE LOCAL COORDINATE SYSTEMS

Fig. 6. Displacements of a loading platform and deformations of a strain beam
As shown in Fig. 6, in the global coordinate system, xyz , the displacement of the origin, o , of the loading platform is Δ

$(\Delta D, \Delta\theta)$, which can be written as

$$\Delta D = [\Delta D_x, \Delta D_y, \Delta D_z]^T = \begin{bmatrix} {}^g\Delta D_x & {}^g\Delta D_y & {}^g\Delta D_z \end{bmatrix}^T, \text{ and (12)}$$

$$\Delta\theta = [\Delta\theta_x, \Delta\theta_y, \Delta\theta_z]^T = \begin{bmatrix} {}^g\Delta\theta_x & {}^g\Delta\theta_y & {}^g\Delta\theta_z \end{bmatrix}^T. \text{ (13)}$$

Here, the displacement of the origin, o_i , of the strain beam is ${}^g\Delta^i$ (${}^g\Delta D^i, {}^g\Delta\theta^i$), which can be written as:

$${}^g\Delta\theta^i = \begin{bmatrix} {}^g\Delta\theta_x^i & {}^g\Delta\theta_y^i & {}^g\Delta\theta_z^i \end{bmatrix}^T, \text{ and (14)}$$

$${}^g\Delta D^i = \begin{bmatrix} {}^g\Delta D_x^i & {}^g\Delta D_y^i & {}^g\Delta D_z^i \end{bmatrix}^T. \text{ (15)}$$

In the local coordinate system, $x_i y_i z_i$, the displacement of origin, o_i , of the strain beam is ${}^i\Delta^i$ (${}^i\Delta D^i, {}^i\Delta\theta^i$), which can be written as:

$${}^i\Delta\theta^i = \begin{bmatrix} {}^i\Delta\theta_x^i & {}^i\Delta\theta_y^i & {}^i\Delta\theta_z^i \end{bmatrix}^T, \text{ and (16)}$$

$${}^i\Delta D^i = \begin{bmatrix} {}^i\Delta D_x^i & {}^i\Delta D_y^i & {}^i\Delta D_z^i \end{bmatrix}^T. \text{ (17)}$$

The relationship between the global displacement, ${}^g\Delta^i$ (${}^g\Delta D^i, {}^g\Delta\theta^i$), of the loading platform and the local displacement, ${}^i\Delta^i$ (${}^i\Delta D^i, {}^i\Delta\theta^i$), of the strain beam is calculated below.

In the global coordinate system, xyz ,

$${}^g\Delta\theta = {}^g\Delta\theta^i = {}^g\Delta\theta^i, \text{ (18)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} {}^g\Delta\theta^i &= Rot(x, y, z) {}^i\Delta\theta^i \\ &= Rot(z, \beta_z^i) Rot(y, \beta_y^i) Rot(x, \beta_x^i) {}^i\Delta\theta^i, \text{ and (19)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} {}^g\Delta D^i &= Rot(x, y, z) {}^i\Delta D^i \\ &= Rot(z, \beta_z^i) Rot(y, \beta_y^i) Rot(x, \beta_x^i) {}^i\Delta D^i. \text{ (20)} \end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} {}^i\Delta\theta^i &= R^T(x, y, z) {}^g\Delta\theta^i \\ &= Rot^T(x, \Delta\beta_x^i) Rot^T(y, \Delta\beta_y^i) Rot^T(z, \Delta\beta_z^i) {}^g\Delta\theta^i \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} c\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i {}^g\Delta\theta_x + c\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i {}^g\Delta\theta_y - s\beta_y^i {}^g\Delta\theta_z \\ (-s\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i) {}^g\Delta\theta_x + (c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i) {}^g\Delta\theta_y + c\beta_y^i s\beta_x^i {}^g\Delta\theta_z \\ (s\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i) {}^g\Delta\theta_x + (-c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i) {}^g\Delta\theta_y + c\beta_y^i c\beta_x^i {}^g\Delta\theta_z \end{bmatrix}, \text{ (21)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} {}^i\Delta D^i &= R^T(x, y, z) {}^g\Delta D^i \\ &= Rot^T(x, \Delta\beta_x^i) Rot^T(y, \Delta\beta_y^i) Rot^T(z, \Delta\beta_z^i) {}^g\Delta D^i \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} c\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i {}^g\Delta D_x + c\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i {}^g\Delta D_y - s\beta_y^i {}^g\Delta D_z \\ (-s\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i) {}^g\Delta D_x + (c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i) {}^g\Delta D_y + c\beta_y^i s\beta_x^i {}^g\Delta D_z \\ (s\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i) {}^g\Delta D_x + (s\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i - c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i) {}^g\Delta D_y + c\beta_y^i c\beta_x^i {}^g\Delta D_z \end{bmatrix}. \text{ (22)} \end{aligned}$$

In the global coordinate system, xyz ,

$${}^g\Delta D^i = {}^g\Delta\theta^i \times r^i + {}^g\Delta D = \begin{bmatrix} r_z^i {}^g\Delta\theta_y - r_y^i {}^g\Delta\theta_z + {}^g\Delta D_x \\ r_x^i {}^g\Delta\theta_z - r_z^i {}^g\Delta\theta_x + {}^g\Delta D_y \\ r_y^i {}^g\Delta\theta_x - r_x^i {}^g\Delta\theta_y + {}^g\Delta D_z \end{bmatrix}. \text{ (23)}$$

Substituting equation (23) in equation (22), then

$${}^i\Delta D^i = Rot^T(x, y, z) ({}^g\Delta\theta^i \times r^i + {}^g\Delta D). \text{ (24)}$$

V. FORCE TRANSFORMATION BETWEEN THE GLOBAL AND THE LOCAL COORDINATE SYSTEMS

In the global coordinate system, the generalize force imposed on the origin, o , of the loading platform is ${}^gQ = [{}^gF, {}^gM]^T$,

which can be written as:

$${}^g F = \begin{bmatrix} {}^g F_x \\ {}^g F_y \\ {}^g F_z \end{bmatrix}^T, \quad (25)$$

$${}^g M = \begin{bmatrix} {}^g M_x \\ {}^g M_y \\ {}^g M_z \end{bmatrix}^T. \quad (26)$$

These are the sum of the forces and torques of all the beams in the global coordinate system.

$${}^g F = \sum_{i=1}^n {}^g F^i = \sum_{i=1}^n {}^g F^i, \quad (27)$$

$${}^g M = \sum_{i=1}^n {}^g M^i = \sum_{i=1}^n ({}^g M_M^i + {}^g M_F^i). \quad (28)$$

The torque imposed on the origin, o , of the loading platform should be separated into two parts:

$${}^g M^i = {}^g M_M^i + {}^g M_F^i. \quad (29)$$

${}^g M_M^i$ represents the torque caused by the local torque,

${}^g M^i$, of the strain beam on o_i in the global coordinate system,

and ${}^g M_F^i$ represents the torque caused by the local force, ${}^g F^i$,

of the strain beam on o_i in the global coordinate system.

Therefore,

$${}^g M_M^i = {}^g M^i, \quad (30)$$

$${}^g M_F^i = r^i \times {}^g F^i. \quad (31)$$

Then,

$${}^g F^i = {}^g F^i = \begin{bmatrix} {}^g F_x^i \\ {}^g F_y^i \\ {}^g F_z^i \end{bmatrix}^T = Rot(x, y, z) {}^o F^i$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} c\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i & -s\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i & s\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i \\ c\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i & c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i & -c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i \\ -s\beta_y^i & c\beta_y^i s\beta_x^i & c\beta_y^i c\beta_x^i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} {}^o F_x^i \\ {}^o F_y^i \\ {}^o F_z^i \end{bmatrix}, \quad (32)$$

$${}^g M^i = \begin{bmatrix} {}^g M_{Mx}^i & {}^g M_{My}^i & {}^g M_{Mz}^i \end{bmatrix}^T = Rot(x, y, z) {}^o M^i$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} c\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i & -s\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i & s\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i \\ c\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i & c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i & -c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i + s\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i \\ -s\beta_y^i & c\beta_y^i s\beta_x^i & c\beta_y^i c\beta_x^i \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} {}^o M_x^i \\ {}^o M_y^i \\ {}^o M_z^i \end{bmatrix}. \quad (33)$$

Where the local force of the beam is transformed from o_i to o in the global coordinate system, the torque on o calculated by the force transformation is given as follows:

$${}^g M_F^i = \begin{bmatrix} {}^g M_{Fx}^i & {}^g M_{Fy}^i & {}^g M_{Fz}^i \end{bmatrix}^T = r^i \times {}^g F^i. \quad (34)$$

VI. SOLUTION

The global force can be calculated in 3 steps [17].

Step 1: Calculation of the global displacement of the loading platform

According to equations (1) and (24), the deformation along x_i of the strain beam in the local coordinate system $x_i y_i z_i$ is

$${}^i \Delta D_x^i = c\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i {}^o \Delta D_x + c\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i {}^o \Delta D_y - s\beta_y^i {}^o \Delta D_z$$

$$+ (-r_y^i s\beta_y^i - r_z^i c\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i) {}^o \Delta \theta_x + (r_x^i c\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i + r_z^i s\beta_y^i) {}^o \Delta \theta_y$$

$$+ (r_x^i c\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i - r_y^i c\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i) {}^o \Delta \theta_z = \frac{{}^o F_x^i l^i}{EA^i} \quad (35)$$

Equation (35) is used to construct a matrix, A_Δ , and a vector, B_Δ .

$$A_\Delta = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11}^\Delta & a_{12}^\Delta & a_{13}^\Delta & a_{14}^\Delta & a_{15}^\Delta & a_{16}^\Delta \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ a_{i1}^\Delta & a_{i2}^\Delta & a_{i3}^\Delta & a_{i4}^\Delta & a_{i5}^\Delta & a_{i6}^\Delta \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ a_{n1}^\Delta & a_{n2}^\Delta & a_{n3}^\Delta & a_{n4}^\Delta & a_{n5}^\Delta & a_{n6}^\Delta \end{bmatrix}, \text{ and} \quad (36)$$

$$B_\Delta = [b_1^\Delta, \dots, b_i^\Delta, \dots, b_n^\Delta]^T. \quad (37)$$

$v_\Delta = \Delta = [\Delta D_x, \Delta D_y, \Delta D_z, \Delta \theta_x, \Delta \theta_y, \Delta \theta_z]^T$, then,

$$A_\Delta v_\Delta = B_\Delta. \quad (38)$$

Where,

$$a_{i1}^\Delta = c\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i; \quad a_{i2}^\Delta = c\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i; \quad a_{i3}^\Delta = -s\beta_y^i; \quad a_{i4}^\Delta = -r_y^i s\beta_y^i - r_z^i c\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i;$$

$$a_{i5}^\Delta = r_x^i c\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i + r_z^i s\beta_y^i; \quad a_{i6}^\Delta = r_x^i c\beta_y^i s\beta_z^i - r_y^i c\beta_y^i c\beta_z^i; \quad b_i^\Delta = \frac{{}^o F_x^i l^i}{EA^i}.$$

The strain beams number is equal to or greater than 6, i.e. $n \geq 6$. The least square method is then used to calculate v_Δ :

$$A_\Delta^T A_\Delta v_\Delta = A_\Delta^T B_\Delta. \quad (39)$$

The global displacement of the loading platform can be calculated using the equation system, (39), given above.

Step 2: Calculation of the local forces in the local coordinate systems

Following the calculation of global displacement Δ , all the local displacements in the local coordinate systems can be calculated using equations (21) and (24).

Furthermore, equations (1), (2), (3), (4), (5) and (6) are used to calculate all the local forces in the local coordinate systems.

It could also be expressed as an equation system, as follows.

$$a_{11}^i = \frac{l^i}{EA^i}, a_{22}^i = \frac{(l^i)^3}{3EI_z^i} + \frac{l^i}{GA^i}, a_{26}^i = \frac{(l^i)^2}{2EI_z^i}, a_{33}^i = \frac{(l^i)^3}{3EI_y^i} + \frac{l^i}{GA^i}, a_{35}^i = \frac{(l^i)^2}{EI_y^i}, \quad (40)$$

$$a_{44}^i = \frac{l^i}{GI_x^i}, a_{55}^i = \frac{(l^i)^2}{2EI_y^i}, a_{55}^i = \frac{l^i}{EI_y^i}, a_{62}^i = \frac{(l^i)^2}{2EI_z^i}, a_{66}^i = \frac{l^i}{EI_z^i}.$$

$$A_{Ni} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11}^i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a_{22}^i & 0 & 0 & 0 & a_{26}^i \\ 0 & 0 & a_{33}^i & 0 & a_{35}^i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & a_{44}^i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & a_{53}^i & 0 & a_{55}^i & a_{56}^i \\ 0 & a_{62}^i & 0 & 0 & 0 & a_{66}^i \end{bmatrix} \quad (41)$$

$$B_{Ni} = [{}^i \Delta D_x^i, {}^i \Delta \theta_x^i, {}^i \Delta D_y^i, {}^i \Delta \theta_y^i, {}^i \Delta D_z^i, {}^i \Delta \theta_z^i]^T \quad (42)$$

$$v_{Ni} = [{}^i F_x^i, {}^i M_x^i, {}^i M_z^i, {}^i F_y^i, {}^i M_y^i, {}^i F_z^i]^T \quad (43)$$

$$A_{Ni} v_{Ni} = B_{Ni} \quad (44)$$

The local force of each beam i can be calculated using equation system(44). The whole equation system for all the beams can be written as:

$$A_N = \begin{bmatrix} A_{N1} & & 0 \\ & \ddots & \\ 0 & & A_{Nn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (45)$$

$$B_N = [B_{N1}^T, \dots, B_{Ni}^T, \dots, B_{Nn}^T]^T \quad (46)$$

$$v_N = [v_{N1}^T, \dots, v_{Ni}^T, \dots, v_{Nn}^T]^T \quad (47)$$

Fig. 8. Calculated force, force error and force random error under an axis-x force

TABLE IV
Random errors of randomly selected sets of forces (Planar)

Set	Inputed			Calculated			Random error		
	$F_x(N)$	$F_y(N)$	$M_z(Nm)$	$F_x(N)$	$F_y(N)$	$M_z(Nm)$	$F_x(N)$	$F_y(N)$	$M_z(Nm)$
1	22.00	58.00	4.50	22.000200	57.999907	4.499999	-2.00E-4	9.26E-5	1.39E-6
2	-17.40	36.50	3.60	-17.399776	36.500212	3.600000	-2.24E-4	-2.12E-4	4.86E-7
3	46.20	-18.90	1.50	46.200059	-18.899992	1.500000	-5.94E-5	-7.80E-6	1.74E-7
4	-18.70	32.60	-3.50	-18.700174	32.600249	-3.500000	1.74E-4	-2.49E-4	0.00
5	78.10	-12.40	-1.30	78.100004	-12.400040	-1.300000	-3.57E-6	4.03E-5	3.12E-7
6	-4.78	32.40	-5.90	-4.780256	32.400009	-5.900002	2.56E-4	-9.23E-6	1.94E-6
7	23.00	84.20	1.80	23.000142	84.200066	1.800000	-1.42E-4	-6.60E-5	-3.12E-7
8	-96.20	0.00	0.50	-96.200000	-6.349E-5	0.500001	-1.15E-7	6.35E-5	-1.04E-6

Fig. 9. Random errors of randomly selected forces, planar structure

The 8 sets of forces were selected at random to calculate the force random errors which are shown in Table IV and Fig. 9. The forces random errors are identical with that which is shown in Fig. 8.

The random errors of forces along both the x axis and y axis are about $0.0006(N)$, and the scale of the measuring range is $\pm 100(N)$. Therefore, the relative errors of F.S. are $0.0006/200 = 0.0003\%$. The random error of torque about the z axis is about $0.000012(Nm)$, and the scale of the measuring range is $\pm 10(Nm)$. Therefore, the relative error of F.S. is $0.000012/20 = 0.00006\%$.

The effective bits of stress data from the FE software are 6, as shown in Table III, making the truncation error 0.0005% .

It was observed that the calculated random errors of the forces and the torque are even smaller than the truncation errors of the initial calculated data from the FE software. We hypothesize that the reason for this is because of the homogenizing effect of the redundant 8 beams used in the structure.

It was shown that almost no errors (including both class I errors, errors in a single axis and class II errors, crosstalk) can be observed in the FE simulation. Work using different FE softwares (Solidworks simulation, Ansys, Abaqus) or utilizing different meshes (the mesh of the beam should be dense enough)

yielded similar results.

Example 2: 3-d structure

Fig. 10. 6-beam 6-axis force sensor

The material of the structure is aluminum alloy 7075, whose properties are shown in Table II.

Fig. 11. Calculated force, and force random error x under an axis-x force

The calculated forces and random errors are shown in Fig. 11.

TABLE V
Random errors of randomly selected sets of forces (3-d)

Set	Inputed						Calculated					
	$F_x(N)$	$F_y(N)$	$F_z(N)$	$M_x(Nm)$	$M_y(Nm)$	$M_z(Nm)$	$F_x(N)$	$F_y(N)$	$F_z(N)$	$M_x(Nm)$	$M_y(Nm)$	$M_z(Nm)$
1	19.0	267.9	-61.2	-13.0	22.5	2.0	19.0047	267.8988	-61.2036	-13.000072	22.500243	2.000045
2	-6.0	112.0	-45.0	-9.0	8.0	7.5	-6.0077	112.0012	-44.9929	-8.99856	7.999556	7.499960
3	248.5	34.8	-23.0	9.6	7.4	-2.0	248.4969	34.8016	-22.9934	9.600022	7.399808	-2.000099
4	98.0	75.0	12.0	8.0	4.0	5.0	98.0064	75.0009	12.0186	8.000004	3.999568	5.000081
5	18.0	-43.0	22.4	-8.3	6.9	4.0	17.9976	-43.0010	22.3984	-8.299941	6.900151	4.000017
6	17.8	26.5	64.0	4.5	6.3	-2.0	-17.8023	26.5027	64.0008	4.500167	6.299991	-2.000155
7	18.0	27.3	109.4	4.0	2.0	1.8	17.9976	27.3013	109.4041	4.000004	1.999924	1.800029
8	64.0	8.0	69.5	7.0	2.0	3.5	64.0076	7.9933	69.4976	6.999895	2.000115	3.500186
9	0.0	3.9	-19.5	5.2	2.2	1.5	-0.0011	3.8989	-19.4943	5.200084	2.199967	1.500061
10	4.8	68.0	39.5	0.0	5.7	3.1	4.7943	67.9999	39.5032	-2.93E-05	5.699709	3.099966

Fig. 12. Random errors of randomly selected forces, 3-d structure

The 10 sets of forces were selected at random to calculate the force random errors which are shown in Table V and Fig. 12.

VIII. CONCLUSION

A calculation method of a redundant parallel beams MAFS is proposed in this paper to calculate the multi-beam MAFSs. Assuming only small deformations of the sensor structure, the global forces, displacements, and local forces appear to operate in an ideal linear relationship, easily and quickly calculable using a linear equation system. The characteristics of such a sensor include a parallel structure of many sensitive strain beams between two rigid platforms. According to the FE

simulation software, the calculated results using this method have theoretically very little crosstalk, and each uniaxial force appears to be ideally linear in nature.

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Redundant parallel beam multi-axis force sensor – Observable variable

Hongwen Ma, and Yuzhuo Xing

Abstract—A universal calculation method of multi-axis force sensor (MAFS) using various sensitive sensors/components is proposed in this paper. An observable variable can be accurately obtained using a sensitive sensor in its local coordinate system. A transformation matrix containing a skew-symmetric operator is applied to transform the space vector using both linear and rotational transformations. Therefore, all the generalized forces and displacements can be transformed between the different coordinate systems. A harmonizing equation system and a solving equation system are proposed using the above transformation matrix. The local displacements in a beam and sensor local coordinate systems can be used to construct the harmonizing equations system. In locations where displacements can be directly measured, it can be selected to construct the solving equations system; Global displacements of the loading platform can be accurately calculated using this system. Subsequently, the local generalized deformations and forces of all beams in the beam local coordinate system can be calculated. Further, the generalized global force can be calculated using the local generalized forces. The solving equations system can be used to construct an observable variable stiffness matrix, which can also be used directly to calculate the generalized global force on the MAFS.

Key words—Displacement sensor, Decoupling placement, Stiffness matrix, Linear elastic system, Finite element analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

MAFS is a most important sensor used in robotics, aerospace, bionics, wind/water tunnel balance, rocket/water jet engine thrust testing, machining, and automobile testing [1].

Various sensitive sensors/components are currently used in MAFSs, which can be classified into strain gauge, piezoelectric crystal, optical, and electrical type sensors. Usually, these sensitive sensors are of low price, convenient placement, and easy application.

The strain gauge type sensor includes a resistance sensor, film sensor, semiconductor sensor, optical sensor, and piezoresistor sensor. The strain gauge type sensor is the most commonly used MAFS because of its high accuracy, wide measuring range, and low cost.

A strain gauge is commonly used in Maltese cross-type integrated MAFSs [2-11], which find a wide range of

applications in commercial products. The E-type sensor is another popular MAFS. Most of E-type MAFSs employ strain gauges as the sensitive components [12-14]. A strain gauge is also used in a few Stewart type MAFSs [15-18] to measure the force along the parallel legs.

Additionally, the strain gauge also finds applications in some other types of MAFSs, such as a three spoke structure [19], six-axis column-type [20], and T-shaped bar [21]. Many special strain gauge type MAFSs are adopted for specific applications such as a polishing robot [22], wind tunnel balance [23-25], human-robot interaction sensor [26], wrist force/torque sensor [27], lab-scale hybrid rocket thrust sensor [28, 29], cutting force sensor [30], robot-assisted sensor [31], and wheel force transducer [32].

A Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) is essentially an optical strain gauge. The FBG is used in fingertip force sensing [33] and haptic sensing in minimally invasive surgeries [34]. A piezoresistor can also be considered as a strain gauge, which is usually applied in MEMS MAFSs [35, 36].

The advantages of piezoelectric crystal type MAFS are high stiffness and high bandwidth.

A four-point support structure piezoelectric crystal MAFS was proposed in [37]. A ring type heavy loading piezoelectric crystal MAFS was proposed in [38]. An eight-piece crystal MAFS was proposed in [39]. A flexible piezoelectric tactile sensor array was proposed in [40].

Optical sensors and components have recently been introduced to MAFSs because of the high accuracy. The FBG has been used as an optical strain gauge in MAFSs [33, 34]. A fiber-optic sensor has been employed in a 3-axis optical force sensor [41, 42]. An optical reflective object sensor has been used in a simply supported beam MAFS [43, 44]. An optical component with one LED and four PDs (photo detectors) has been used in a three-symmetrical link MAFS [45]. The LED and PDs have also been used in underwater MAFSs [46]. An integrating four-photo-interrupter has been used in a cross-shaped three-axis force sensor [47]. The photo-interrupter has been also used in some uniaxial torque sensors [48, 49].

Currently, electrical type MAFS mainly comprise capacitive and Hall type sensors. Usually, the accuracy of a capacitive sensor is high and the cost of a Hall sensor is low. Six-capacitive sensor cells have been adopted to detect three normal

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and three shear forces in a six-axis force sensor (6AFS) [50]. A similar capacitive structure was proposed in [51] with a different elastomer structure. A miniature 6AFS has been adopted in a surgical palpation probe using a capacitance sensor [52]. MEMS multi-axis force/acceleration sensors are generally capacitive type sensors. A set of RC networks was used in [53]. A silicon six-axis force–torque sensor with capacitance was developed in [54]. A micromachined electrostatically-suspended three-axis accelerometer was developed in [55]. A MEMS MAFS for a microrobot was developed in [56]. A large range of biomechanical applications for 6AFS were developed in [57, 58].

A Hall element is usually used in soft tactile MAFSs. A soft force sensor comprising magnetic powder blended with silicone rubber was developed in [59]. A soft fingertip with tactile sensation was developed in [60]. A soft magnetic, powdery sensor for tactile sensing was developed in [61]. A magnetic field-based soft tactile sensor was developed in [62].

The advantages of these sensors are of low price, convenient placement and easy application. Therefore, they are widely used in various fields. The decoupling idea is proposed in most studies, for example, an optoelectronic component in [45, 46], a capacitive sensor cell in [50-52]. The multi-axis force can be calculated by a decoupling placement of these sensors. According to the method illustrated in [1], high accuracy sensors/components and decoupling placement in the sensor local coordinate system are also of importance in highly precise MAFSs, such as a confocal optical sensor [63, 64], a triangular optical sensor [65, 66], a capacitive sensor containing a guard ring [67], an eddy current sensor [68], a high precision CCD [69], and a quadrant position detector (QPD) [70].

A calculation method for the sensitive sensors/components mentioned above is proposed in this paper. The main aspects of this calculation method are as follows: establishing a local coordinate system for the sensor similar to the one used for the beam; a coordinate transformation method; a deformation harmonizing equations system; a displacement solving equations system; and an observable variable stiffness matrix. The harmonizing equations are established using a coordinate transformation method between the global coordinate system and the beam/sensor local coordinate system. The solving equation is selected in locations where some observable variables in the harmonizing equations can be physically measured by a sensitive sensor or component. All the selected equations can then be used to construct a solving equation system. The displacements of the loading platform can be calculated using the solving equation system and it can be used to calculate the deformations and forces of all the beams in the local coordinate system. Following transformation of all the local beam forces into global forces, the sum of all global forces in the beams is the generalized force in the MAFS. After obtaining the solution equations system, it can be used to construct an observable variable stiffness matrix. This matrix can be used to directly calculate the generalized force in the MAFS [71, 72].

II. BEAM AND SENSOR LOCAL COORDINATE SYSTEMS

Fig. 1 Coordinate transformation of a strain beam

Fig. 2 Local coordinate systems of both a strain beam and a capacitive sensor

A coordinate transformation is illustrated in Fig. 1 which is the same with that in Paper 1 [1]. Therefore, the beam position and posture in the global coordinate system can be expressed as

$$r^i = [r_x^i, r_y^i, r_z^i]^T \text{ and } \beta^i = [\beta_x^i, \beta_y^i, \beta_z^i]^T.$$

A sensitive sensor with a local coordinate system $x_j y_j z_j$ is detailed in Fig. 2. The position and posture of $x_j y_j z_j$ in the global coordinate system are similar to that of the beam with the coordinates $r^j = [r_x^j, r_y^j, r_z^j]^T$ and $\beta^j = [\beta_x^j, \beta_y^j, \beta_z^j]^T$. It is evident that the sensitive axis of the capacitive sensor in Fig.2 is along the x_j axis.

III. SPACE VECTOR TRANSFORMATION

The generalized force and deformation can be expressed as,

$${}^g Q = [{}^g F_x, {}^g F_y, {}^g F_z, {}^g M_x, {}^g M_y, {}^g M_z]^T, \text{ and}$$

$${}^g \Delta = [{}^g \Delta D_x, {}^g \Delta D_y, {}^g \Delta D_z, {}^g \Delta \theta_x, {}^g \Delta \theta_y, {}^g \Delta \theta_z]^T.$$

Various space vector transformations, such as screw theory [73], can be applied to calculate the displacement and force transformation between in the different coordinate systems. A simple skew-symmetric operator is used in this paper [74]. The deformation displacement of the beam in its local coordinate system is,

$${}^i \Delta^i = T_g^i {}^g \Delta, \quad (1)$$

Where

$$T_g^i = \begin{bmatrix} Rot(\beta^i) & S(r^i)Rot(\beta^i) \\ 0 & Rot(\beta^i) \end{bmatrix}.$$

$$S(r^i) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -r_z^i & r_y^i \\ r_z^i & 0 & -r_x^i \\ -r_y^i & r_x^i & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ is a skew-symmetric matrix, and}$$

$$\text{Rot}(\beta^i) = \text{Rot}(\beta_z^i) \text{Rot}(\beta_y^i) \text{Rot}(\beta_x^i).$$

Similarly, the displacement of the sensor in its local coordinate system is,

$${}_{o_j}^j \Delta^j = T_g^j {}_o \Delta. \quad (2)$$

IV. STIFFNESS MATRIX OF THE MAFS

According to equations (1) ~ (6) in paper 1 [1], the deformation of the beam can be written as,

$${}_{o_i}^i \Delta^i = {}_{o_i}^i c^i {}_{o_i}^i Q^i. \quad (3)$$

Where

$${}_{o_i}^i c^i = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{l^i}{EA^i} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{(l^i)^3}{3EI_z^i} + \frac{l^i}{GA^i} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{(l^i)^2}{2EI_z^i} \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{(l^i)^3}{3EI_y^i} + \frac{l^i}{GA^i} & 0 & \frac{(l^i)^2}{2EI_y^i} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{l^i}{GI_p^i} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{(l^i)^2}{2EI_y^i} & 0 & \frac{l^i}{EI_y^i} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{(l^i)^2}{2EI_z^i} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{l^i}{EI_z^i} \end{bmatrix}.$$

${}_{o_i}^i c^i$ is the compliance matrix. The stiffness matrix at point, o_i in the local coordinate system is,

$${}_{o_i}^i k^i = [{}_{o_i}^i c^i]^{-1} \quad (4)$$

The stiffness matrix at point o in the global coordinate system is,

$${}_{o}^g k^i = (T_i^g)^T {}_{o_i}^i k^i T_i^g \quad (5)$$

The stiffness matrix of the 6AFS at point o in the global coordinate system is,

$${}_{o}^g k = \sum_{i=1}^n {}_{o}^g k^i \quad (6)$$

V. DEFORMATION HARMONIZING EQUATIONS SYSTEM

According to the transformation, T_g^i , equation system (1) can be expressed as,

$$\begin{cases} c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i {}_o \Delta_x + c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i {}_o \Delta_y - s\beta_z^i {}_o \Delta_z + (-r_z^i s\beta_x^i - r_x^i c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i) {}_o \Delta_\theta_x \\ + (r_z^i c\beta_x^i c\beta_z^i + r_x^i s\beta_x^i) {}_o \Delta_\theta_y + (r_z^i c\beta_x^i s\beta_z^i - r_x^i c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i) {}_o \Delta_\theta_z \\ \hline (c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i s\beta_z^i - c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i) {}_o \Delta_x + (c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i + s\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i) {}_o \Delta_y + c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i {}_o \Delta_z \\ + (-r_z^i c\beta_x^i c\beta_z^i - r_x^i s\beta_x^i s\beta_z^i + r_y^i c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i) {}_o \Delta_\theta_x + r_x^i c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i s\beta_z^i - r_z^i c\beta_x^i s\beta_z^i {}_o \Delta_\theta_y \\ + (r_z^i c\beta_x^i c\beta_z^i + r_x^i s\beta_x^i s\beta_z^i - r_x^i c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i) {}_o \Delta_\theta_z \\ \hline (c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i s\beta_z^i + s\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i) {}_o \Delta_x + (c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i s\beta_z^i - c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i) {}_o \Delta_y + c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i {}_o \Delta_z \\ + (r_z^i c\beta_x^i c\beta_z^i + r_x^i c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i - r_z^i c\beta_x^i s\beta_z^i) {}_o \Delta_\theta_x + (-r_z^i c\beta_x^i c\beta_z^i + r_x^i c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i s\beta_z^i + r_x^i s\beta_x^i s\beta_z^i) {}_o \Delta_\theta_y \\ + (-r_z^i c\beta_x^i s\beta_z^i - r_x^i s\beta_x^i s\beta_z^i - r_z^i c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i s\beta_z^i + r_x^i c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i) {}_o \Delta_\theta_z \\ \hline c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i {}_o \Delta_\theta_x + c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i {}_o \Delta_\theta_y - s\beta_z^i {}_o \Delta_\theta_z \\ \hline (c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i s\beta_z^i - c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i) {}_o \Delta_x + (c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i + s\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i) {}_o \Delta_y + c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i {}_o \Delta_z \\ \hline (c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i s\beta_z^i + s\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i) {}_o \Delta_x + (c\beta_z^i s\beta_x^i s\beta_z^i - c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i) {}_o \Delta_y + c\beta_z^i c\beta_x^i {}_o \Delta_z \end{cases} = {}_o^i \Delta D_x^i \quad (7)$$

It can be simplified as,

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}^{ADx} {}_o \Delta D_x + a_{12}^{ADx} {}_o \Delta D_y + a_{13}^{ADx} {}_o \Delta D_z + a_{14}^{ADx} {}_o \Delta \theta_x + a_{15}^{ADx} {}_o \Delta \theta_y + a_{16}^{ADx} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^i \Delta D_x^i & (a) \\ a_{11}^{ADy} {}_o \Delta D_x + a_{12}^{ADy} {}_o \Delta D_y + a_{13}^{ADy} {}_o \Delta D_z + a_{14}^{ADy} {}_o \Delta \theta_x + a_{15}^{ADy} {}_o \Delta \theta_y + a_{16}^{ADy} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^i \Delta D_y^i & (b) \\ a_{11}^{ADz} {}_o \Delta D_x + a_{12}^{ADz} {}_o \Delta D_y + a_{13}^{ADz} {}_o \Delta D_z + a_{14}^{ADz} {}_o \Delta \theta_x + a_{15}^{ADz} {}_o \Delta \theta_y + a_{16}^{ADz} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^i \Delta D_z^i & (c) \\ a_{14}^{AD\theta_x} {}_o \Delta \theta_x + a_{15}^{AD\theta_x} {}_o \Delta \theta_y + a_{16}^{AD\theta_x} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^i \Delta \theta_x^i & (d) \\ a_{14}^{AD\theta_y} {}_o \Delta \theta_x + a_{15}^{AD\theta_y} {}_o \Delta \theta_y + a_{16}^{AD\theta_y} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^i \Delta \theta_y^i & (e) \\ a_{14}^{AD\theta_z} {}_o \Delta \theta_x + a_{15}^{AD\theta_z} {}_o \Delta \theta_y + a_{16}^{AD\theta_z} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^i \Delta \theta_z^i & (f) \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Equation system (2) could be expressed and simplified as,

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}^{ADx} {}_o \Delta D_x + a_{12}^{ADx} {}_o \Delta D_y + a_{13}^{ADx} {}_o \Delta D_z + a_{14}^{ADx} {}_o \Delta \theta_x + a_{15}^{ADx} {}_o \Delta \theta_y + a_{16}^{ADx} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^j \Delta D_x^j & (a) \\ a_{11}^{ADy} {}_o \Delta D_x + a_{12}^{ADy} {}_o \Delta D_y + a_{13}^{ADy} {}_o \Delta D_z + a_{14}^{ADy} {}_o \Delta \theta_x + a_{15}^{ADy} {}_o \Delta \theta_y + a_{16}^{ADy} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^j \Delta D_y^j & (b) \\ a_{11}^{ADz} {}_o \Delta D_x + a_{12}^{ADz} {}_o \Delta D_y + a_{13}^{ADz} {}_o \Delta D_z + a_{14}^{ADz} {}_o \Delta \theta_x + a_{15}^{ADz} {}_o \Delta \theta_y + a_{16}^{ADz} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^j \Delta D_z^j & (c) \\ a_{14}^{AD\theta_x} {}_o \Delta \theta_x + a_{15}^{AD\theta_x} {}_o \Delta \theta_y + a_{16}^{AD\theta_x} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^j \Delta \theta_x^j & (d) \\ a_{14}^{AD\theta_y} {}_o \Delta \theta_x + a_{15}^{AD\theta_y} {}_o \Delta \theta_y + a_{16}^{AD\theta_y} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^j \Delta \theta_y^j & (e) \\ a_{14}^{AD\theta_z} {}_o \Delta \theta_x + a_{15}^{AD\theta_z} {}_o \Delta \theta_y + a_{16}^{AD\theta_z} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^j \Delta \theta_z^j & (f) \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

We call (8) and (9) as a deformation harmonizing equations system. The system indicates that equations including global displacements as variables can be established in positions where some of the local deformation displacements can be observed.

The planar structure deformation harmonizing equations system for the beam is expressed as,

$$\begin{cases} \cos(\beta_z^i) {}_o \Delta D_x + \sin(\beta_z^i) {}_o \Delta D_y + (-r_z^i \cos(\beta_z^i) + r_x^i \sin(\beta_z^i)) {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^i \Delta D_x^i & (a) \\ -\sin(\beta_z^i) {}_o \Delta D_x + \cos(\beta_z^i) {}_o \Delta D_y + (r_z^i \sin(\beta_z^i) + r_x^i \cos(\beta_z^i)) {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^i \Delta D_y^i & (b) \\ {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^i \Delta \theta_z^i & (c) \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

, which can be simplified as,

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}^{ADx} {}_o \Delta D_x + a_{12}^{ADx} {}_o \Delta D_y + a_{13}^{ADx} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^i \Delta D_x^i & (a) \\ a_{11}^{ADy} {}_o \Delta D_x + a_{12}^{ADy} {}_o \Delta D_y + a_{13}^{ADy} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^i \Delta D_y^i & (b) \\ a_{13}^{AD\theta_z} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^i \Delta \theta_z^i & (c) \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Thus, the relevant equations system for the sensor is,

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}^{ADx} {}_o \Delta D_x + a_{12}^{ADx} {}_o \Delta D_y + a_{13}^{ADx} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^j \Delta D_x^j & (a) \\ a_{11}^{ADy} {}_o \Delta D_x + a_{12}^{ADy} {}_o \Delta D_y + a_{13}^{ADy} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^j \Delta D_y^j & (b) \\ a_{13}^{AD\theta_z} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = {}_o^j \Delta \theta_z^j & (c) \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

For example, in positions where ${}_{o_i}^i \Delta D_x^i$ and ${}_{o_j}^j \Delta D_x^j$ can be measured using the sensitive sensors and components shown in Fig.2, equations (11)(a) and (12)(a) are the selected deformation harmonizing equations. In fact, equations (8)(a) and (11)(a) were used in Paper 1 [1].

VI. DISPLACEMENT SOLVING EQUATIONS SYSTEM

The following equations can be selected to establish a new equations system in locations where some observable variables on the right of the equation systems (8) or (9) can be measured as mentioned above.

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}^{\Delta} {}_o \Delta D_x + a_{12}^{\Delta} {}_o \Delta D_y + a_{13}^{\Delta} {}_o \Delta D_z + a_{14}^{\Delta} {}_o \Delta \theta_x + a_{15}^{\Delta} {}_o \Delta \theta_y + a_{16}^{\Delta} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = \delta_1 \\ \vdots \\ a_{h1}^{\Delta} {}_o \Delta D_x + a_{h2}^{\Delta} {}_o \Delta D_y + a_{h3}^{\Delta} {}_o \Delta D_z + a_{h4}^{\Delta} {}_o \Delta \theta_x + a_{h5}^{\Delta} {}_o \Delta \theta_y + a_{h6}^{\Delta} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = \delta_h \\ \vdots \\ a_{H1}^{\Delta} {}_o \Delta D_x + a_{H2}^{\Delta} {}_o \Delta D_y + a_{H3}^{\Delta} {}_o \Delta D_z + a_{H4}^{\Delta} {}_o \Delta \theta_x + a_{H5}^{\Delta} {}_o \Delta \theta_y + a_{H6}^{\Delta} {}_o \Delta \theta_z = \delta_H \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

All the coefficients in equations system (13) are equal to the selected equations coefficients in (8), (9), (11) and (12). δ_h is the observable variable same to ${}_{o_j}^j \Delta D_x^j$ in its local coordinate

system. Thus, the equations system (13) can be expressed as

$$[a]_o^g \Delta = \delta. \quad (14)$$

Where, for a 3-d structure,

$$[a] = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11}^\Delta & a_{12}^\Delta & a_{13}^\Delta & a_{14}^\Delta & a_{15}^\Delta & a_{16}^\Delta \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ a_{h1}^\Delta & a_{h2}^\Delta & a_{h3}^\Delta & a_{h4}^\Delta & a_{h5}^\Delta & a_{h6}^\Delta \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ a_{H1}^\Delta & a_{H2}^\Delta & a_{H3}^\Delta & a_{H4}^\Delta & a_{H5}^\Delta & a_{H6}^\Delta \end{bmatrix}, \text{ and } \delta = \begin{bmatrix} \delta_1 \\ \vdots \\ \delta_h \\ \vdots \\ \delta_H \end{bmatrix},$$

and for a planar structure,

$$[a] = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11}^\Delta & a_{12}^\Delta & a_{13}^\Delta \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ a_{h1}^\Delta & a_{h2}^\Delta & a_{h3}^\Delta \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ a_{H1}^\Delta & a_{H2}^\Delta & a_{H3}^\Delta \end{bmatrix}, \text{ and } \delta = \begin{bmatrix} \delta_1 \\ \vdots \\ \delta_h \\ \vdots \\ \delta_H \end{bmatrix}.$$

We call the system (14) as a displacement solving equations system. The displacements of the loading platform in the global coordinate system can be solved by employing such an equation system using the least square method.

$$[a]^T [a]_o^g \Delta = [a]^T \delta. \quad (15)$$

The calculated displacements of the loading platform can be expressed as:

$$_o^g \Delta = \left([a]^T [a] \right)^{-1} [a]^T \delta. \quad (16)$$

Further, the generalized force in the global coordinate system is

$$_o^g Q = {}_o^g k {}_o^g \Delta = {}_o^g k \left([a]^T [a] \right)^{-1} [a]^T \delta = {}_o^g K \delta. \quad (17)$$

Then,

$$_o^g K = {}_o^g k \left([a]^T [a] \right)^{-1} [a]^T. \quad (18)$$

Where, ${}_o^g k$ is the stiffness matrix for the MAFS, as shown in equation (6).

We call ${}_o^g K$ as an observable variable stiffness matrix.

The equations system (17) indicates that in positions where δ can be measured accurately, ${}_o^g Q$ can be calculated accurately. The equation system appears to be identical to the conventional calculation equations system containing a decoupling matrix. However, the conventional decoupling matrix cannot be derived strictly, which indicates that the observed variables cannot possess a strictly linear relationship with the measuring forces. This is one of the major reasons for the large crosstalk observed in conventional MAFSs. Thus, an accurate observable variable and a strict relationship between the observable variable and global force under the theory and elastic mechanics are vital.

Where δ is measured, an alternative method to calculate ${}_o^g Q$ is given as follows: 1) Calculation of ${}_o^g \Delta$ using equation system (14); 2) The same calculation method in Section VI from Paper 1 [1].

VII. OBSERVABLE VARIABLES IN THE LOCAL COORDINATE SYSTEM

Fig. 3 Coupling placement of a total-reflection-spot angular sensor

The accurate observable variable and the strict relationship mentioned above are vital for an accurate measurement. Therefore, a decoupling displacement measurement in the local coordinate system is important. As show in Fig. 3, because the measurement is affected by both the rotation about the z_i axis and the displacement along the x_j axis, the placement of the displacement sensor is a coupling placement.

Fig. 4 Decoupling placement of a total-reflection-spot angular sensor

A decoupling total-reflection-spot angular sensor is shown in Fig. 4. The emitted laser beam is perpendicular to the object surface, it indicates that the measurements only depend on the rotation of the object. The displacements along axes x_j and y_j do not affect the measurements or the affection is a second order infinitesimal that can be omitted

Fig. 5 Placement of a planner capacitive sensor, a dial gauge, an optical triangular sensor and an optical confocal sensor.

Fig. 6 Placement of a 3-d capacitive sensor, a capacitive sensor with guard ring, a CCD and a 3-d total-reflection-spot sensors. Picture (b) is from the website "https://www.micro-epsilon.com/".

Several decoupling precise sensitive sensors can be used as observing sensors in a MAFS. A capacitive sensor, a micro force displacement sensor, a triangular optical sensor, and a confocal optical sensor are illustrated in Fig. 5. All these sensors are sensitive along the x_i axis and are insensitive along/about the other axes. Usually, A high collimation laser beam is superior to a simple light emitting diode, a QPD or a high-resolution CCD are more accurate than a simple photo transistor, and a capacitive with a guard ring has a minimal

coupling between different axes. Some dual-axes displacement sensors are shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 7 Strain gauge placement of a planar strain beam

TABLE I

SELECTABLE EQUATION FROM DEFORMATION HARMONIZING EQUATIONS SYSTEM OF A PLANAR STRAIN BEAM

	Placement in Figure.6	Selectable equation in equations system(11)
	(a)	(a)
	(b)	(a),(b) or (a),(c)
	(c)	(a),(b),(c)
	(d)	(a),(b),(c)

Fig. 8 Strain gauge placement of a 3-d strain beam

TABLE II

Selectable equation from deformation harmonizing equations system of a 3-d strain beam

	Placement in Figure.7	Selectable equation in equations system(8)
	(a)	(a),(e) or (a),(f)
	(b)	(a),(e),(f)
	(c)	(d)
	(d)	(a),(b),(c),(e),(f)
	(e)	(a),(b),(c),(d),(e),(f)
	(f)	(a),(b),(c),(d),(e),(f)
	(g)	(a),(b),(c),(d),(e),(f)

The accuracy of a strain gauge is generally lower than that of

the high precision sensors and components, such as an optical confocal sensor or a capacitive sensor with a guard ring. However, it is widely employed in MAFS because of its low cost.

Fig. 7 shows a planar strain beam with various strain gauge placements. Some of the observable variables can be obtained based on the placement type, as shown in Table I. Similarly, the strain gauge placement types for a 3-d strain beam are shown in Fig. 8, and the observable variables are listed in Table II.

Fig. 9 High accuracy strain gauge placement about/along the beam axial line

The accuracy of the observable variable along the axial line in the local beam coordinate system can be improved using the gauge placement type shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 10 Local coordinate system of a piezoelectric crystal

Fig. 11 Soft material block with a capacitive sensor

A piece of piezoelectric crystal is shown in Fig. 10; it should be noted that any crystal type possessing shear or compression effect can be used. For example, when a crystal with compression effect is used, the deformation along the axis x_i can be calculated by equation (1) from Paper 1 [1]. It follows that equation (8)(a) is a selectable harmonizing equation, which can be used to construct the solving equation system. A soft thick block with a capacitive sensor, as shown in Fig. 11, can also be considered as an accurate strain beam. The two polar plates are printed directly onto both sides of the soft block. The capacitor is a decoupling sensor, which is only affected by the compression effect. The accuracy is high because of the guard ring. Equation (1) from Paper 1 [1] and equation (8)(a) can also be adopted for such a block beam.

VIII. TYPICAL LAYOUTS OF SENSITIVE SENSORS AND BEAMS

Fig. 12 Strain gauge type MAFS

Fig. 13 Capacitive sensor type MAFSs

Fig. 14 Piezoelectric crystal / soft block type MAFSs

Fig. 15 Combination of different strain beams and different sensitive sensors/components in MAFSs

Two strain gauge type MAFSs were illustrated in Paper 1 [1]. Even one cantilever beam can be considered as an accurate 6AFS when using the strain gauge placement type (e), (f), or (g) in Table III or in Fig. 8. However, the disadvantage of such a single cantilever beam sensor is its considerably low stiffness about the x axis and along/about the y and z axes. The disadvantage of a planar 6-beam structure 6AFS, as shown in

Fig.12(a), is the low stiffness along the z axis and about the x and y axes. By contrast, the disadvantage of a 3-beam structure 6AFS in Fig.11(b) is the low stiffness about the x , y , and z axes. However, the accuracy of these 6AFSs can be considerably high by using the correct strain gauge placement type or the correct sensitive sensor/component. Moreover, the thickness of the beam can be increased along with an increase in the stiffness along/about all of the x , y , and z axes. For example, the beam thickness along the z axis can be increased in Fig.12 (a) with an apparent increase in the stiffness about x , y and along z axes. The decoupling layout of strain gauge is important. Fig.12 (a) ① is an unsuitable layout which indicates that F_z , M_x and M_y cannot be solved by such a layout. If only the sum of a strain gauge pair ($\varepsilon = \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2$) is considered as one observable variable, F_z , M_x and M_y also cannot be solved, on the contrary, if ε_1 and ε_2 are considered as observable variables respectively, all the forces can be solved. Similarly, Fig.12(b) ① is also an unsuitable layout, and M_z cannot be calculated by such a layout.

Four types of capacitive MAFSs are shown in Fig.13. The capacitive sensor can also include the types shown in Fig.5(a), Fig.6(a) and Fig.6(b).

Two thick-beam-type MAFSs are shown in Fig.14, where a piezoelectric crystal, as shown in Fig.10, and a soft block, as shown in Fig.11, can be employed. If no capacitor is printed on the soft block, some standalone sensors/components can be used as the sensitive sensors, as shown in Fig.14(b).

Different types of beams with strain gauges and sensitive sensors can be combined in one 6AFS, as shown in Fig.15, according to the calculation equation (17). For a planar MAFS, three observable variables are sufficient, while for a 3-d MAFS, six variables should be used. Generally speaking, more accurate observable variables can increase the accuracy of a MAFS.

IX. FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATION

Example 1: Planar structure

Fig. 16 Planar MAFS with capacitive sensors

TABLE III
PARAMETERS OF THE CAPACITIVE SENSOR STRUCTURE

j	1	2	3	4
r_x^j (mm)	0	-22	0	22
r_y^j (mm)	22	0	-22	0
β_z^j (°)	0	90	180	-90

The mechanical structure in Fig.16 is exactly the same as the planar structure in Paper 1 [1] along with the material of the structure. Four capacitive sensors are used to calculate the

generalized force on the MAFS. The parameters of these capacitive sensors are shown in Table III.

TABLE IV

OBSERVABLE VARIABLE STIFFNESS MATRIX ${}^o K$ (10^7 N/M), ABOUT THE FOUR CAPACITORS

3.016059941066323	-0.669472666749996	-1.677358899722227	-0.669372859033748
-0.683549836518535	3.030382417881349	-0.683260336420588	-1.663382931310888
-0.011172807110967	-0.032888624060277	-0.011173309233855	-0.032888805215946

The observable variable stiffness matrix in equation (18) is used directly to calculate the global generalized forces, which are shown in Table IV.

The calculation method using strain gauges is the same as the one used in Paper 1 [1]. It is clear that the observable variable stiffness matrix can also be applied using strain gauges.

TABLE V

CALCULATED GENERALIZED FORCES UNDER A PARTICULAR LOADING WITH STRAIN GAUGES AND CAPACITORS RESPECTIVELY, (-45N, 10N, 6Nm)

	$F_x(N)$	$F_y(N)$	$M_z(Nm)$	
Input forces	-45	10	6	
Calculated forces by strain gauge	-44.9997886881065	10.0000475844392	5.99999444640363	
Calculated forces by capacitors	-45.0007793831829	10.0007989589604	5.99999228264499	
Measured stress along axis x_i (10^6 N/m ²)	$i = 1$	$i = 2$	$i = 3$	$i = 4$
	2.55268	-2.07600	2.43729	-1.68870
	$i = 5$	$i = 6$	$i = 7$	$i = 8$
	1.76910	-2.24541	1.88381	-2.63309
Measured displacement along axis x_j (10^{-6} m)	$j = 1$	$j = 2$	$j = 3$	$j = 4$
	-7.76802	-6.59537	-5.85048	-7.02144

A particular loading is simulated along with the calculation results shown in Table V.

Eight sets of forces were randomly selected to calculate the random errors in these forces using strain gauges and capacitors. The selected forces are the same as those in Table IV of Paper 1 [1].

TABLE VI

CALCULATED RESULTS BY STRAIN GAUGES AND CAPACITORS RESPECTIVELY USING 8 SETS OF RANDOMLY SELECTED INPUT FORCES (PLANAR)

Set	Inputed			Calculated using strain gauge			Random error using strain gauge		
	$F_x(N)$	$F_y(N)$	$M_z(Nm)$	$F_x(N)$	$F_y(N)$	$M_z(Nm)$	$F_x(N)$	$F_y(N)$	$M_z(Nm)$
1	22.00	58.00	4.50	22.000200	57.999907	4.499999	-2.00E-4	9.26E-5	1.39E-6
2	-17.40	36.50	3.60	-17.399776	36.500212	3.600000	-2.24E-4	-2.12E-4	-4.86E-7
3	46.20	-18.90	1.50	46.200059	-18.899992	1.500000	-5.94E-5	-7.80E-6	1.74E-7
4	-18.70	32.60	-3.50	-18.700174	32.600249	-3.500000	1.74E-4	-2.49E-4	0.00
5	78.10	-12.40	-1.30	78.100004	-12.400040	-1.300000	-3.57E-6	4.03E-5	3.12E-7
6	-4.78	32.40	-5.90	-4.780256	32.400009	-5.900002	2.56E-4	-9.23E-6	1.94E-6
7	23.00	84.20	1.80	23.000142	84.200066	1.800000	-1.42E-4	-6.60E-5	-3.12E-7
8	-96.20	0.00	0.50	-96.200000	-6.349E-5	0.500001	-1.15E-7	6.35E-5	-1.04E-6
Set	Inputed			Calculated using capacitor			Random error using capacitor		
	$F_x(N)$	$F_y(N)$	$M_z(Nm)$	$F_x(N)$	$F_y(N)$	$M_z(Nm)$	$F_x(N)$	$F_y(N)$	$M_z(Nm)$
1	21.999653	58.000186	4.499996	3.47E-4	-1.86E-4	4.25E-6			
2	-17.400373	36.500370	3.599994	3.73E-4	-3.70E-4	5.52E-6			
3	46.199882	-18.899975	1.500000	1.18E-4	-2.49E-5	3.36E-7			
4	-18.699693	32.599304	-3.499997	-3.07E-4	6.95E-4	-2.57E-6			
5	78.100054	-12.400077	-1.300001	-5.38E-5	7.66E-5	1.05E-6			
6	-4.779597	32.399303	-5.899997	-6.03E-4	6.97E-4	-3.40E-6			
7	23.000052	84.200171	1.800000	-5.17E-5	-1.71E-4	4.71E-7			
8	-96.200064	4.196E-05	0.500000	6.36E-5	-4.20E-5	4.61E-7			

Fig. 17 Random errors of random selected forces

The results we have calculated are shown in Table VI and Fig.17. It can be seen that the random errors calculated using the capacitors are slightly higher than those calculated using the strain gauges. This is because only four capacitors are applied in the MAFS. Therefore, the homogenizing effect is not apparent. The truncation error of both the capacitor and strain gauge are identical in the simulation. However, in practice the accuracy of a capacitor is much higher than a strain gauge. This means that a MAFS with high precision sensors and components is more accurate.

Further, the information obtained from the capacitors and strain gauges can be combined to calculate the generalized force. For example, three observable variables using two capacitors and one strain beam with two strain gauges are sufficient to calculate the planar generalized force. Generally speaking, more accurate observable variables can increase the accuracy of a MAFS.

Example 2: 3-d structure

Fig. 18 3-d MAFS with laser displacement sensors

The mechanical structure in Fig.18 is exactly the same as the 3-d structure in Paper 1 [1] along with the material of the structure. Six laser displacement sensors are used to calculate the generalized force on the MAFS.

TABLE VII

CALCULATED RESULTS BY STRAIN GAUGES AND DISPLACEMENT SENSOR RESPECTIVELY USING 10 SETS OF RANDOMLY SELECTED INPUT FORCES (3-D)

Set	Inputed						Calculated using strain gauge					
	$F_x(N)$	$F_y(N)$	$F_z(N)$	$M_x(Nm)$	$M_y(Nm)$	$M_z(Nm)$	$F_x(N)$	$F_y(N)$	$F_z(N)$	$M_x(Nm)$	$M_y(Nm)$	$M_z(Nm)$
1	19.0	267.9	-61.2	-13.0	22.5	2.0	19.0047	267.8988	-61.2036	-13.00072	22.50024	2.000045
2	-6.0	112.0	-45.0	-9.0	8.0	7.5	-6.0071	112.0012	-44.9929	-8.99856	7.999556	7.499960
3	248.5	34.8	-23.0	9.6	7.4	-2.0	248.4969	34.8016	-22.9934	9.600022	7.399808	-2.000099
4	98.0	75.0	-12.0	8.0	-4.0	5.0	98.0064	75.0009	-12.0186	8.000004	-3.999568	5.000081
5	76.0	-43.0	22.4	-8.3	6.9	4.0	76.0023	-43.0010	22.3984	-8.299941	6.900151	4.00017
6	18.0	27.3	109.4	4.0	2.0	1.8	17.9976	27.3013	109.4041	4.000004	1.999924	1.800029
7	-17.8	26.5	64.0	4.3	6.3	-2.0	-17.8023	26.5027	64.0008	4.500167	6.299991	-2.000158
8	64.0	8.0	69.5	7.0	2.0	3.5	64.0026	7.9933	69.4976	6.999895	2.000115	3.500186
9	0.0	3.9	-19.5	5.2	2.2	1.5	-0.0011	3.8989	-19.4943	5.200084	2.199967	1.500061
10	4.8	68.0	39.5	0.0	5.7	3.1	4.7943	67.9999	39.5032	-2.93E-05	5.699709	3.099966
Set	Inputed						Calculated using laser displacement sensor					
	$F_x(N)$	$F_y(N)$	$F_z(N)$	$M_x(Nm)$	$M_y(Nm)$	$M_z(Nm)$	$F_x(N)$	$F_y(N)$	$F_z(N)$	$M_x(Nm)$	$M_y(Nm)$	$M_z(Nm)$
1	19.0011	267.9001	-61.1952	-13.000130	22.500128	2.000005						
2	-6.0028	111.9988	-45.0074	-8.998735	7.999718	7.500022						
3	248.5014	34.8011	-23.0069	9.600025	7.399957	-2.000057						
4	98.0012	74.9995	-11.9937	7.999831	-3.999766	5.000025						
5	75.9995	-43.0003	22.4027	-8.299999	6.900022	4.000009						
6	18.0002	27.3010	109.3972	4.000073	1.999962	1.8000091						
7	-17.8004	26.5001	63.9994	4.500075	6.300002	-2.000088						
8	63.9972	7.9968	69.5128	6.999780	1.999986	3.500127						
9	-0.0027	3.9003	-19.4988	5.200079	2.199904	1.500056						
10	4.7986	68.0007	39.4940	6.03E-05	5.698853	3.100037						

Ten sets of forces were randomly selected to calculate the random errors in these forces using strain gauges and laser displacement sensor. The selected forces are the same as those in Table V of Paper 1 [1]. The results we have calculated are shown in Table VII.

X. CONCLUSION

The generalized force on a MAFS can be accurately calculated using various sensors in a precise placement. Where an accurate observable variable and a strict relationship between the observable variable and the global force are obtained, the accurate generalized force imposed on the MAFS can be calculated.

A displacement harmonizing equations system and a deformation solving equation system are proposed using a transformation matrix with a skew-symmetric operator. In locations where local displacement in the harmonizing equations system can be accurately measured, the equation can be selected to construct the solving equation system. Further, the global displacements of the loading platform can be accurately calculated using the solving equation system. Subsequently, the local generalized deformations and forces for all beams can be calculated in the local coordinate system. The generalized global force can be calculated using the local generalized forces. In addition, the solving equation system can be used to construct an observable variable stiffness matrix. This matrix can also be used to directly calculate the generalized global force on the MAFS.

According to an FE simulation, the results calculated using the method outlined above are sufficiently accurate.

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Redundant parallel beam multi-axis force sensor – Loading offset

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Abstract—The crosstalk in various structures is detailed in this paper. A pseudo rigid zone with a very small deformation supporting a loading force is vital in each of the loading platform and the supporting platform. The change in the stiffness matrix of a MAFS is the main reason for crosstalk. All the changes in the mechanical clearance, local contact surface, and local deformation states can affect the stiffness matrix; therefore, they are unsuitable in a precise MAFS. A loading offset indicates the change of the loading force location on the loading platform. Because of the unavoidable loading offset, although the stiffness matrix is a constant matrix for a fixed loading location, it changes profoundly according to the loading offset. Three methods can be used to make the change in the stiffness matrix sufficiently small: 1) obtaining the exact position of the loading offset, but this is usually difficult, 2) enlarging the size of the loading platform, and 3) increasing the elasticity modulus of the loading platform and decreasing that of the strain beam. It is shown according to the simulations that the accuracy of a MAFS is higher using a softer or thin beam.

Key words—Pseudo rigid zone, Compliance/stiffness matrix, Elastic half space, Coupling

I. INTRODUCTION

MAFS is a most important sensor used in robotics, aerospace, bionics, wind/water tunnel balance, rocket/water jet engine thrust testing, machining, and automobile testing etc. [1-2]

Many MAFSs are decoupled using a mechanical joint, such as a Stewart parallel structure with a mechanical joint [3, 4], a three-dimensional parallel structure [5], a parallel mechanism with a steel ball structure [6], and a cross-beam elastomer structure with a ball bearing [7, 8]. The advantages of these structures are of high stiffness, low cost and simple decoupling structure.

Some other MAFSs have an integrated structure, such as a Stewart parallel structure with a flexure joint [9-14], an E-type structure [15-17], the Maltese cross structure [18-27], a cross-shaped type [28, 29], a T-shaped bar [30], a frame/truss type [31], a wheel force transducer [32], a high dynamic range type [33], and a column type [34]. The advantages of such structures are of no frictional force and no dynamic contact surface between the two components.

Because of these advantages, these structures are widely used in various applications. Certainly, the crosstalk should be

further studied.

This paper discusses the crosstalk from the perspective of the change in the stiffness matrix. A redundant parallel beam structure with an accurate mechanical model is proposed by Ma [1, 2]. It is essentially an integrated structure. According to the finite element simulation, such a structure can be considered as an ideal linear elastic structure. However, such a linear elastic character is based on the assumption of a rigid loading platform and a rigid supporting platform. The change in the imposed loading zone on the loading platform will affect the measurements. The reason for this is that the stiffness of the loading platform is not infinite, and the force transmission is related to the stiffness of the platform. Therefore, a study of the stiffness of the loading and supporting platforms is vital.

A loading offset is unavoidable in practice as the stiffness matrix shifts because of the loading offset. Usually, high stiffness in a loading platform, along with low stiffness in a beam, can counteract the influence of the loading offset on the loading platform. The mechanical clearance and contact state change in a contact surface will lead to a beam loading offset, which is similar to a loading offset on the loading platform. Therefore, a constant stiffness matrix in the inner structure of a MAFS is vital, and the inner structure should be designed carefully, especially considering the change of stiffness in the force transmission path rather than only considering the loading capacity.

II. BEAM COMPLIANCE/STIFFNESS MATRIX

Fig. 1. Cantilever beam

According to the Euler beam theory, the compliance matrix of a cantilever beam [2], as shown in Fig. 1, is:

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$${}^i c_{el}^i = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{l^i}{EA} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{(l^i)^3}{3EI_z^i} + \frac{l^i}{GA^i} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{(l^i)^2}{2EI_z^i} \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{(l^i)^3}{3EI_y^i} + \frac{l^i}{GA^i} & 0 & \frac{(l^i)^2}{2EI_y^i} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{l^i}{GI_v^i} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{(l^i)^2}{2EI_y^i} & 0 & \frac{l^i}{EI_y^i} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{(l^i)^2}{2EI_z^i} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{l^i}{EI_z^i} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

III. ELASTIC HALF-SPACE AND COMPLIANCE/STIFFNESS MATRIX OF THE PLATFORMS

Each loading and supporting platform can be regarded as an elastic half-space.

Fig. 2. Elastic half-space

An elastic half-space with a rigid rectangular plane is shown in Fig. 2. A general force is imposed on the rigid plane. The deformation in the half-space decreases gradually at the location where it is far from the rigid rectangle plane.

$\Delta = [\Delta D_x, \Delta D_y, \Delta D_z, \Delta \theta_x, \Delta \theta_y, \Delta \theta_z]^T$ is the generalized displacement of the rigid rectangle plane.

$Q = [F_x, F_y, F_z, M_x, M_y, M_z]^T$ is the generalized force imposed on the rigid rectangle plane.

$$\Delta = c Q. \quad (2)$$

Where c is the compliance matrix of the elastic half-space.

Fig. 3. Stiffness of an elastomer

${}^i c_{lo}^i$ and ${}^i c_{su}^i$ are the compliance matrixes of the loading and supporting platforms respectively as shown in Fig. 3.

$${}^i c_{lo}^i = \begin{bmatrix} {}^i c_{lo11}^i & \cdots & {}^i c_{lo16}^i \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ {}^i c_{lo61}^i & \cdots & {}^i c_{lo66}^i \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

$${}^i c_{su}^i = \begin{bmatrix} {}^i c_{su11}^i & \cdots & {}^i c_{su16}^i \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ {}^i c_{su61}^i & \cdots & {}^i c_{su66}^i \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

The parameters in the matrix can be obtained using Mindlin's or Boussinesq's solutions or can be calculated using FE software. Usually, such an elastic half-space can be considered as a linear elastic system.

IV. ELASTOMER STIFFNESS

The compliance of the whole elastomer, including the beam and two deformation zones of both the loading and supporting platforms, is

$${}^i c_{el}^i = {}^i c_{be}^i + {}^i c_{lo}^i + T_i^i {}^i c_{su}^i (T_i^i)^T. \quad (5)$$

Where T_i^i indicates the vector transformation from the coordinate $x_i y_i z_i$ to $x_i y_i z_i$ [2].

The stiffness of the elastomer is

$${}^i k_{el}^i = ({}^i c_{el}^i)^{-1} \quad (6)$$

Only the stiffness of the beam, ${}^i k_{be}^i$ is considered within the calculation method by Ma in Paper 1 and 2 [1, 2] along with two rigid platforms. It is a reason why the calculated results using FE simulation usually need a linear correction in the studies by Ma.

V. PSEUDO RIGID ZONE

Fig. 4. Pseudo rigid zone of the platforms

It can be observed that in the location far from the strain beams, the loading, and the supporting base, the deformation in the platform becomes smaller, as shown in Fig. 4.

The precondition for an accurate mechanics model illustrated by Ma [1, 2] is the assumption of the rigid loading and supporting platforms. However, no rigid body exists in practice. Whether the loading and supporting platforms can be considered as rigid bodies depends on the influence of the deformations on the accuracy of the MAFS.

A judgment criterion is illustrated below. The loading platform can be separated into a loading deformation zone, a pseudo rigid zone, and beam deformation zones along with a supporting deformation zone, a pseudo rigid zone, and beam deformation zones on the supporting platform, as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 5. Deformation triangular in a pseudo rigid zone

A pseudo rigid zone on either the loading or the supporting platform is a continuous zone; each deformation zone is isolated from the others by the pseudo rigid zone.

Assume a generalized force Q is imposed on the MAFS. Points A, B, and C are randomly selected points on a pseudo rigid zone, as shown in Fig. 5. The deformation ratio of the triangle ABC is

$$\delta_{ABC} = \max \left(\frac{\Delta l_{AB}}{l_{AB}}, \frac{\Delta l_{BC}}{l_{BC}}, \frac{\Delta l_{CA}}{l_{CA}}, \frac{\Delta \angle A}{\angle A}, \frac{\Delta \angle B}{\angle B}, \frac{\Delta \angle C}{\angle C} \right). \quad (7)$$

The deformation ratio of a pseudo rigid zone is defined as

$$\delta_{PRZ} = \max(\nabla \delta_{ABC}). \quad (8)$$

Fig. 6. Deformation tetrahedron in a pseudo rigid zone

For a 3D structure, the deformation ratio of a pseudo rigid zone is defined using a tetrahedron, as shown in Fig. 6.

$$\delta_{ABCD} = \max(\delta_{ABC}, \delta_{ABD}, \delta_{ACD}, \delta_{BCD}). \quad (9)$$

The deformation ratio of a pseudo rigid zone on either a loading or supporting platform is

$$\delta_{PRZ} = \max(\nabla \delta_{ABCD}). \quad (10)$$

Fig. 7. Key points in a pseudo rigid zone

Indeed, it is impossible to verify all the points on a platform. Usually, some key points are sufficient to detect the deformation ratio of a pseudo rigid zone, as shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 8. Deformation of thin beam

The deformation ratio of a thin beam, as shown in Fig. 8 is

$$\delta_{beam} = \Delta l_1 / l_1. \quad (11)$$

Fig. 9. Deformation of a thick beam

For a thick beam, the deformation ratio of the beam is similar to that of the pseudo rigid zone, as shown in Fig. 9.

$$\delta_{ABC} = \max \left(\frac{\Delta l_{AB}}{l_{AB}}, \frac{\Delta l_{BC}}{l_{BC}}, \frac{\Delta l_{CA}}{l_{CA}}, \frac{\Delta \angle A}{\angle A}, \frac{\Delta \angle B}{\angle B}, \frac{\Delta \angle C}{\angle C} \right) \quad (12)$$

For a planar beam,

$$\delta_{beam} = \max(\nabla \delta_{ABC}). \quad (13)$$

For a 3D beam,

$$\delta_{beam} = \max(\nabla \delta_{ABCD}). \quad (14)$$

Usually, the top points of the beam can be regarded as the key points.

The deformation ratio of all the beams is

$$\delta_{beams} = \max(\delta_{beam_1}, \dots, \delta_{beam_i}, \dots, \delta_{beam_N})$$

The criterion for whether a suitable pseudo rigid body exists in a platform is that $\delta_{PRZ} \ll \delta_{beams}$ or $\delta_{PRZ} / \delta_{beams} \ll 1$ when any permitted force, Q , is imposed on the loading platform.

Generally speaking, assume the relative accuracy of the MAFS is a , and the relative deformation ratio between the pseudo rigid body and the beams in any permitted force, Q , is

$$\delta_{rdr} = \max(\delta_{PRZ} / \delta_{beams}, \nabla Q) < a. \quad (15)$$

Indeed, it is impossible to impose all the permitted force, Q , on the MAFS; some combination of the extreme forces/torques along/about the x , y , and z axes can be used to calculate the relative deformation ratio. Usually, formula (15) is not a strict criterion. Where more sensitive components are affixed on a MAFS, the accuracy of the MAFS can be sufficiently accurate even if the relative deformation ratio is slightly higher.

Generally speaking, the relative deformation ratio can be regarded as an indicator to detect whether the stiffness of a pseudo rigid body on a loading or a supporting platform is sufficiently high.

Fig. 10. Pseudo rigid zone in different size platforms

Regarding what is mentioned above, the beam and the loading and supporting deformation zones should be sufficiently large to increase the accuracy of the MAFS. It indicates that the accuracy of the MAFS in Fig. 10 (a) is usually higher than that in Fig. 10 (b).

VI. STRUCTURE DISCUSSION OF CONVENTIONAL MAFSS

Fig. 11. Couplings of conventional MAFSS

A precise MAFS needs an excellent mechanical structure, as shown in Fig. 11 (a), with the following essential aspects.

1. Isolation of the loading deformation zone and each beam deformation zone by a pseudo rigid zone in the loading platform, along with the isolation in the supporting platform.
2. Stiffness invariance along the force transmission path.
3. Decoupling structure of a series elastomer.

The shortcomings of the conventional MAFSS are illustrated as follows.

1. Coupling among beams and deformation zones, as shown in Fig. 11 (b). Indeed, such a coupling can usually be corrected to a certain degree. The symbols of the degree of coupling are shown in Fig. 12.

Fig. 12. Degree of coupling

Fig. 13. Coupling of series structures

Fig. 14. Coupling of parallel structures

Fig. 15. Coupling of flexure hinge structures

The coupling degrees of series structures, parallel structures, and flexure-hinge structures are shown in Fig. 13, Fig. 14, and Fig. 15, respectively.

2. Coupling between a beam and a loading/supporting structure, as shown in Fig. 11 (c).

3. Weaker loading/supporting platforms, as shown in Fig. 11 (d).

4. Stiffness variance of a contact surface.

Regarding what is mentioned above, the stiffness variance will affect the measurement of the sensitive component dramatically, and the structure of such an MAFS will not be considered as a linear elastic structure anymore.

- (1) Static connection structure

Fig. 16. Separation of a contact surface connected with bolts by a force

As shown in Fig.16, when a permitted force is imposed on a beam, some zones of the contact surface will be separated. Such a phenomenon is unsuitable for a precise MAFS.

Fig. 17. Complex contact surfaces of a bolt

As shown in Fig.17, the use of a bolt should be considered carefully. The contact stiffness of all the contacted surfaces in locations 1, 2, 3, and 4 is easily changed by changing the loading force.

Fig. 18. Acceptable bolt connection structure

Indeed, as shown in Fig. 18, if the contact surface is very large, many thick bolts are used to fix the contact surface, and the preloading of these bolts is sufficiently high; usually, such a bolt connection structure is acceptable.

(2) Dynamic connection structure

Besides the strong frictional force, the contact stiffness is dramatically affected by a dynamic connection structure.

Fig. 19. Clearance fit connection

As shown in Fig. 19, the contact surface is a clearance fit. First, the clearance will affect the contact stiffness profoundly; second, the change of the contact area will also affect the contact stiffness.

Fig. 20. Interference fit connection

Although an interference fit can eliminate the clearance, as shown in Fig. 20, it will lead to many other shortcomings. First, the frictional force will increase; second, because of the deformation of the contact surface by the loading, the contact stiffness still cannot be a constant.

Fig. 21. Point-contacted structure

Some point-contacted structures have similar shortcomings as those mentioned above as shown in Fig. 21.

5. Complex coupling

Fig. 22. Coupling of the Maltese cross type MAFSS

The beams in the Maltese cross MAFSS can be considered as a series-parallel structure. The cross point is a coupling structure, as shown in Fig. 22.

Fig. 23. Stiffness curve along the x axis

Generally speaking, a complex inner structure will usually lead to a complex inner coupling. Although they have many advantages, such as a simple decoupling structure, easily machining, and low cost, they can hardly be considered as perfect structures for a precise MAFSS as shown in Fig. 23. However, if the MAFSS is calibrated in a particular point, the stiffness curves around the calibration point along/about the x, y, and z axes in a small range can still be about regarded as linear relations.

VII. OUTER LOADING AND SUPPORTING FRAMES

The loading and supporting platforms of an MAFSS are relatively weak, as shown in Fig. 24. However, if both the outer loading and supporting frames are sufficiently strong, and the connections can be regarded as ideal bonded connections (by welding or many powerful bolts), the accuracy of such an MAFSS can still be sufficiently high.

Fig. 24. Ideal connection with a loading and a supporting frames

Fig. 25. Identical forces imposed on different zones

Either the upper or lower platform can be considered as a loading platform along with the other as a supporting platform, as shown in Fig. 25. The discriminating criterion is on which platform the impact force is imposed. For example, an impact force is imposed on different zones of the upper platform. Therefore, the upper platform is considered as the loading platform.

Supposing the three forces, F_1 , F_2 and F_3 , are identical in the global coordinate system, oxy . They are imposed on different zones on the loading platform respectively, as shown in Fig. 27. Since the three forces are identical, the measured stresses in the beams should also be similar to obtain a nearly equal calculated results. For such a planar structure, the stress decreases according to the distance to the second power from the force imposed zone for the planar structure. As a consequence, if the relative accuracy influence of a 2-mm loading offset should be smaller than $1/10^4$, the distance from the beam to the permitted

loading zone should be more than $2 \times \sqrt{10^4} = 200$ mm. In this way, the relatively deformation ratio in equation (15) can be sufficiently small. It indicates that the accuracy of a MAFS is strongly depended on the offset of the loading imposed zone and the size of the loading platform.

Fig. 26. Methods for decreasing the influence of a loading force offset

Considering the relative deformation ratio in equation (15), if the beam material is very soft along with a hard material for the loading platform, the size of the loading platform can be decreased, as shown in Fig. 26 (a). For example, supposing the elasticity modulus of the beam is of that of the loading platform, the size of the loading platform can be of the original size to obtain the same influence for a planar structure. A relatively long extension beam can homogenize the loading better, as shown in Fig. 26 (b). The soft beam can also be installed, as shown in Fig. 26 (c) and (d).

All the other couplings, except the loading offset, can be easily restrained by a carefully designed redundant parallel beam structure.

IX. LOADING OFFSET

On the whole, the offset of the imposed loading zone will affect the accuracy of the MAFS, and it should be an important indicator of a MAFS.

For example, two identical forces, F_1 and F_2 , in the global coordinate system, are imposed on different zones of the same MAFS, as shown in Fig. 29 (a) and (b); the relationship between the measured force and the offset is an important indicator.

The offset of the two forces is s , which is used as an indicator to analyze the influence on the MAFS's accuracy. An even force in a small area is used to simulate the concentrated force, as shown in Fig. 29 (b). It indicates that only the magnitude of the force along the x - or y - or about the z -axis can be changed. The distribution type of force cannot be changed. Indeed, the distribution of the force can be any type; an even force type is only used for a simple application in the FE software.

The structure appears to be a linear elastic system for a fixed loading offset, however, the stiffness matrix differs for various loading offsets, as shown in Figure. 27 (c). The loading offset is like a mechanical clearance, as shown in Fig. 7, Fig. 8, Fig. 10, Fig. 11, and Fig. 12, which is unavoidable for an outside loading force. Indeed, what we hope is that the offset can be determinate, or it has a sufficiently small influence on the stiffness matrix.

Fig. 27. Loading offset on a loading platform

Based on the above analysis, we can draw the following viewpoints.

If the stiffness of the loading platform is infinite (a rigid loading platform) or the loading offset is guaranteed to be 0, the stiffness matrix of a MAFS can be an ideal constant matrix, and the accuracy of the MAFS is trending to 0; certainly, it is difficult. To guarantee the offset to be about 0, perhaps an on-site celebration proposed by some companies is necessary in some particular applications. Certainly, perhaps the on-site celebration equipment should be carefully designed and provided to the customers by these companies. All the couplings proposed in section VI should be carefully considered in such an on-site celebration method.

If the size of the loading platform can be sufficiently large for a constant loading offset, the variance of the stiffness curve can be sufficiently small, and the accuracy of the MAFS can be sufficiently high.

If the stiffness of all the beams can be sufficiently low along with a sufficiently high stiffness of the loading platform, the variance of the stiffness curve can also be sufficiently small; however, the loading capacity and the loading stiffness of the MAFS are also small.

Except for the outer loading offset, all the fatal inner factors which can lead to a stiffness variance should be eliminated.

X. FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATION

Example 1: Planar structure

Two kinds of planar structure with alloy steel and rubber beams respectively are simulated to show that a MAFS with a

sufficiently high stiffness loading platform along with a sufficiently low stiffness beam can be considered as an accurate MAFS even with a large loading offset.

Fig. 28. MAFSs with an alloy steel beam and a rubber beam respectively

The structure in Fig.28 (a) is the same with that in papers 1 and 2 [1, 2], except the thickness and material of the beam. The thickness is 2mm, and the material is alloy steel. As a matter of fact, the thickness and material of the beam have a minimal influence on the MAFS's accuracy. Such a structure is still a linear elastic structure.

The identical forces in the global coordinate system are imposed on the different zones of the loading platform. The loading offset is s . The following calculation is based on the four capacitive sensors.

The loading, supporting platforms, and beams are an integrated structure. The material of the whole structure is alloy steel.

The stiffness matrix about the four capacitive sensors where $s = 0$ mm is shown in Table I. The calculated results for various offsets are shown in Table II. Apparently, the accuracy of calculated force is affected by the loading offset. Certainly, if the offset position is known, it is very easy to obtain the stiffness matrix about such an offset, and then calculate an accurate result using such a stiffness matrix, however, the offset position can hardly be predetermined.

TABLE I
OBSERVABLE VARIABLE STIFFNESS MATRIX ${}^s K$ (10^7 N/M), ABOUT THE FOUR CAPACITORS, ALLOY STEEL BEAM, WHERE $s = 0$ MM

2.85141178917709	0.16142400718723	-3.17224401800602	0.16149250809239
-1.30073001105583	4.30346860025271	-1.30138755717260	-1.71928703428597
0.02369280649527	0.03032683365902	0.02369229719827	0.03032806357575

Elastic Modulus = $2.1e+11$ N/m²

TABLE II
CALCULATED FORCE IN VARIOUS OFFSET WITH AN INPUT FORCE (1N, 0N, 0Nm) IN THE GLOBAL COORDINATE SYSTEM, ALLOY STEEL BEAM

Offset s (mm)	F_x (N)	F_y (N)	M_z (Nm)
0.0	0.9999989571	-1.9776507623e-07	-6.3674295191e-09
0.1	0.9999594497	-0.0002552225	-5.9036334555e-07
0.3	0.9998373729	-0.0007674550	-1.7114493163e-06
1.0	0.9990076147	-0.0025845216	-5.3493734340e-06
3.0	0.9929562866	-0.0084523044	-9.1265368499e-06

Regarding what is mentioned above, a large loading platform can be used to decrease the influence of a force offset, or beams with relatively low stiffness can be applied to realize the same purpose. A rubber beam is used to replace the alloy steel beam, as shown in Fig. 30 (b). Suppose the beam is ideally connected

with both the loading and the supporting platforms.

TABLE III

OBSERVABLE VARIABLE STIFFNESS MATRIX ${}^s K$ (10^4N/M), ABOUT THE FOUR CAPACITORS, RUBBER BEAM, WHERE $s = 0 \text{ MM}$

1.23631526983199	0.06304046939467	-1.36139441089838	0.06304086253369
0.41213991262847	0.882647237651989	0.41214150466799	-1.71505739442947
0.00833886778434	0.016541386184764	0.00833889683881	0.01654128781072

Elastic Modulus = $6.1 \times 10^6 \text{ N/m}^2$

The stiffness matrix about the four capacitive sensors where $s = 0 \text{ mm}$ is shown in Table III. The calculated results for various offsets are shown in Table IV. The errors of the calculated force by the offset are profoundly decreased. Indeed, the stiffness and loading capacity of the MAFS also decreased.

TABLE IV

CALCULATED FORCE IN VARIOUS OFFSET WITH AN INPUT FORCE (1N, 0N, 0NM) IN THE GLOBAL COORDINATE SYSTEM, RUBBER BEAM

Offset s (mm)	F_x (N)	F_y (N)	M_z (Nm)
0.0	0.9999999862	1.1068069221e-07	1.7335167200e-09
0.1	0.9999987245	1.6211733621e-05	3.6220954524e-08
0.3	0.9999948427	4.8804371322e-05	1.1435973274e-07
1.0	0.9999792481	0.0001632772308	4.0915875550e-07
3.0	0.9999389404	0.0004904709654	1.3630382013e-06

Fig.31. Embedded rubber beam structure

Various structures can be applied for such a composite structure [35]; an example is shown in Figure 31.

Example 2: 3-d structure

Fig.32. MAFS with a 3-d structure

TABLE V

CALCULATED FORCE IN VARIOUS OFFSET WITH AN INPUT FORCE (0N, 0N, 10N, 0NM, 0NM, 0NM) IN THE GLOBAL COORDINATE SYSTEM, THICK BEAM

s (mm)	F_x (N)	F_y (N)	F_z (N)	M_x (Nm)	M_y (Nm)	M_z (Nm)
0.0	1.31e-07	1.88e-04	9.999699	1.13e-07	4.02e-06	-4.50e-06
0.1	2.57e-04	2.33e-04	9.998670	-1.13e-06	1.21e-05	-3.23e-06
0.3	8.74e-05	1.82e-04	9.996229	-8.92e-06	4.45e-06	-3.79e-06
1.0	1.72e-04	2.28e-04	9.988134	-1.57e-05	-4.98e-06	-4.70e-06
3.0	1.75e-04	1.53e-04	9.953433	-6.02e-05	-1.88e-04	-3.80e-06

TABLE VI

CALCULATED FORCE IN VARIOUS OFFSET WITH AN INPUT FORCE (0N, 0N, 10N, 0NM, 0NM, 0NM) IN THE GLOBAL COORDINATE SYSTEM, THIN BEAM

s (mm)	F_x (N)	F_y (N)	F_z (N)	M_x (Nm)	M_y (Nm)	M_z (Nm)
0.0	2.95e-06	-1.02e-06	9.999997	-9.17e-08	-7.24e-08	3.62e-08
0.1	5.26e-05	-2.64e-05	9.998887	2.77e-07	1.56e-06	-1.53e-06
0.3	5.45e-05	-9.00e-05	9.996518	-4.02e-06	-7.24e-07	-8.45e-07
1.0	6.73e-05	-8.38e-05	9.988357	-1.37e-05	-1.30e-05	-1.00e-06
3.0	1.15e-04	-1.34e-05	9.953682	-5.35e-05	-1.95e-04	-6.77e-07

The structure in Fig.32 (a) is the same with that in papers 1 and 2 [1, 2], along with a thin beam structure in Fig.32 (b). The calculated forces in various offset using both the thick and the thin beam structures are shown in Table V and Table VI respectively.

XI. CONCLUSION

A redundant parallel beam structure can be considered as an ideal linear elastic structure without a loading force offset or with an ideal rigid loading platform.

A loading platform with high stiffness along with a beam with low stiffness has a small influence on the accuracy of a MAFS enduring a loading offset. A large loading platform also has a small influence on the accuracy of a MAFS enduring a loading offset.

An ultra-precise MAFS can be realized with a sufficiently high stiffness loading platform, a sufficiently low stiffness beam, and a sufficiently large-size loading platform.

The mechanical clearance, the dynamic connection, and the unsuitable static connection should be avoided in a precise MAFS.

In the design of a MAFS, the loading offset, the loading capacity, and the accuracy should be considered overall. Further, the platform material, beam material, size of the structure, type of the sensitive component, and placement of the sensitive components can be determined. All of these should be studied further.

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Redundant parallel beam multi-axis force sensor – Distributed sensing system

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Abstract—A distributed multi-axis force-sensing system (DMAFSS) is proposed in this paper. An individual MAFS with a small loading neck can be regarded as a sufficiently accurate sensor. All of the generalized pseudo-point-concentrated forces measured by these MAFSs can be unified into one coordinate system using a sensor frame. The sensor frame is isolated from all of the MAFSs by an isolation structure. A calculation method to unify all of the measured forces by these precise, stand-alone MAFSs is also proposed. A displacement-solving equation system for the unification is derived based on the space vector transformation and precision measurement. Decoupling high precise displacement sensors are fixed on the sensor frame to obtain the observable variables for the displacement-solving equations system. The sensor frame of large, ground force-measuring equipment can be fixed on the ground far away from the supporting frame, and the sensor frame of mobile force-measuring equipment can be fixed on the supporting frame or loading frame by an isolation structure (damping structure). Therefore, the sensor frame can be regarded as a pseudo-rigid body.

Key words—Pseudo-rigid body, Point-concentrated force, Isolation structure, Observable variable

I. INTRODUCTION

MAFS is a most important sensor used in robotics, aerospace, bionics, wind/water tunnel balance, rocket/water jet engine thrust testing, machining, and automobile testing etc. [1-3]

MAFSs can be classified by size, into small-scale and a large-scale configurations. A small-scale MAFS is usually utilized in a force-control robot, an exoskeleton, an automobile crash acceleration sensing system or a minimally-invasive surgery robot, for instance. A large-scale MAFS is usually applied in a wind/water tunnel balance, thrust engine testing stand, or a huge force-control manipulator.

Generally speaking, the force imposed on a model in a wing/water tunnel, a testing bed in a thrust stand, or a huge manipulator, is distributed across a large-scale range.

According to the location where a MAFS is placed in a tunnel, the wind/water tunnel balance is classified into an internal balance and external balance. The internal balance can be regarded as simply a universal, six-axis force sensor [4, 5]. Some external balances are also universal six-axis force sensors that are connected to the models using a thick supporting pole [6]. The loading capacity of such an external balance is small

and the thick supporting pole seemingly affects the wind stream. The other external balances with multiple supporting poles are distributed, MAFs [7~9]. A suspension force-measuring system is proposed by Liu [10]. It is a large-scale distributed sensing system. A multi-support balance is proposed by Li [11], where multiple individual MAFSs are applied to calculate the generalized force of the measured object. All of the individual MAFSs are decoupled by some mechanical joints. Meanwhile, four three-axis piezoelectric sensors are used to measure the six-component force of a wind tunnel balance by Gao [12]. An external, six-component strain gauge balance is proposed by Samardžić [13]. Six single-force load cells are connected to the loading frame through the rods and pivot flexures. A similar six-component wind tunnel balance was deployed in a NASA project, the Tiltrotor Test Rig, by Solis [14].

A six-component jet rig balance was designed by Ramaswamy [15], where six single-dimensional load cell were employed to connect the loading platform by six links. A similar structure is applied by Wright in [16, 17].

The large measurement range of MAFS for wider applications in aircraft landing, rocket thrust stand, spacecraft docking testing and wind tunnel testing has become an urgent objective. A Six-Universal-Prismatic-Universal-Revolute joints six-axis force sensor with flexible joints was developed by Zhao in [18, 19]. In turn, a bidirectional-decoupling, over-constrained, six-dimensional parallel-mechanism force sensor is developed by Niu [20]. A parallel piezoelectric, six-axis heavy force/torque sensor is developed by Li in [21, 22]. Meanwhile, Stewart-type MAFSs are developed by Yao in [23~25].

The idea of distributed structure and distributed calculation method is proposed in most of these multi-axis force sensors which points out the direction of this study.

A distributed, multi-axis force-sensing system with both relatively high accuracy and high loading capacity is proposed in this paper for the highly accurate measurement of a multi-axis distributed force. Multiple pseudo-point-concentrated-force, multi-axis force sensors are used to measure the distributed loading force imposed on a loading frame. The distributed loading force can be transformed into multiple pseudo-point-concentrated forces that can be accurately measured by a stand-alone MAFS with a small loading neck. A pseudo-rigid sensor frame is used to unify all of the point-concentrated force into one coordinate system. The sensor

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frame is isolated by the loading force by using an isolation structure. A deformation harmonizing equations system and a displacement solving equations system for the MAFSs are then proposed for the unification of multiple, point-concentrated forces in the sensor frame coordinate system.

II. PRECISE PSEUDO POINT-CONCENTRATED FORCE MAFS

Fig. 1. Precise MAFS with a loading neck

Fig. 2. Various loading necks with mechanical joints, flexure hinges and over-constrained structures

Assuming a loading force is concentrated in a point, as shown in Fig.1 (a), the MAFS can be regarded as an absolutely accurate sensor [3]. Indeed, the size of a loading zone cannot be zero. As is shown in Fig.1 (b), if the loading neck (diameter of the neck on the loading platform), d , is sufficiently small, the distance, D , is sufficiently large, or the strain beam is sufficiently soft; and so the accuracy of the MAFS is sufficiently high. Although, for a particular distributed loading force and a particular contact condition between the loading object (loading frame) and MAFS, even the loading neck is large, while the loading offset can still be minimal. However, for a generalized condition, a better method to make the loading offset sufficiently small is to make the loading neck sufficiently small. It would seem that the loading offset is equal to or smaller than the loading neck. Indeed, the loading capacity of such an MAFS is minimal.

Various precise MAFSs are shown in Fig. 2. Although a mechanical hinge or an over-constrained structure is not a suitable structure as an inner structure of a stand-alone MAFS, they can be suitable for connecting a loading platform and loading frame. The reason for this is that the frictional force is regarded as an outer loading that can be measured accurately by a stand-alone MAFS.

III. DISTRIBUTED MULTI-AXIS FORCE SENSING SYSTEM

Fig. 3. Distributed MAFSs located on a rigid supporting frame

Although the structure shown in Fig. 1 (b) can be regarded as a precise MAFS, the loading capacity, especially the torque capacity of such a structure, is minimal. A distributed multi-axis force-sensing system (DMAFSS) can improve the loading capacity, as is shown in Fig. 3.

Compared to the deformation of the loading frame, the deformation of a stand-alone MAFS is usually minimal, and therefore the MAFS is regarded as a rigid body in the case of such a DMAFSS. Assuming the supporting frame to be a rigid body, and that all of the distributed MAFSs are fixed on the rigid frame, the global generalized force of the entire sensing system is,

$${}^g_oQ = \sum_{k=1}^K T_k^g {}^k_oQ^k \quad (1)$$

Where T_k^g indicates the force transformation matrix from a MAFS coordinate system, $x_k y_k z_k$, to the global coordinate system, xyz .

Unfortunately, no rigid body exists in practice. Therefore, both the supporting frame and the ground are deformed for supporting a loading force by a loading object.

IV. SENSOR FRAME

Fig. 4. Deformation of the distributed multi-axis force sensing system

The deformation of the structure supporting a loading force is shown in Fig. 4. Therefore, the actual global generalized force of the entire sensing system is,

$${}^g Q = \sum_{k=1}^K T_{o_k}^{g, k'} Q^k \quad (2)$$

$$T_{o_k}^{g, k'} = \begin{bmatrix} Rot(\beta^{k'}) & S(r^{k'}) Rot(\beta^{k'}) \\ 0 & Rot(\beta^{k'}) \end{bmatrix}.$$

Where ${}^{k'} Q^k$ indicates the practical force in the practical local MAFS coordinate system, $o_k X_k Y_k Z_k$. $T_{o_k}^{g, k'}$ indicates the transformation matrix from the coordinate system $o_k X_k Y_k Z_k$ to the global coordinate system, $oxyz$. The initial position and posture parameters, r^k and β^k , can be calibrated accurately; however, the practical position and posture parameters, $r^{k'}$ and $\beta^{k'}$, must be accurately measured in real time.

Fig. 5. Sensor frame in a DMAFSS

As is shown in Fig. 5, a number of displacement sensors are used to measure the real-time position and posture of an MAFS, with all of the displacement sensors fixed on a sensor frame. The sensor frame is far away (and/or isolated) from the supporting frame on the ground. Therefore, the deformation of the ground by the supporting frame has minimal influence on the sensor frame, and the sensor frame can be regarded as a pseudo-rigid body. The displacements of the MAFSs can be measured accurately by these displacement sensors fixed to the sensor frame. The measuring method is similar to that illustrated by Ma [3] using a capacitive sensor, an optical triangular sensor, a laser total reflection sensor, or a high-precision CCD.

Fig. 6. Layout of displacement sensors on the sensor frame

Three layouts of sensors on a sensor frame are shown in Fig. 6. Usually, the stability in Fig. 6 (a) is better, while the accuracy in Fig. 6 (b) is high, and although both the stability and accuracy in Fig. 6 (c) are superior, the structure is relatively complex. Usually, if the strain beam of an MAFS is very soft, the deformation between the loading platform and supporting platform is larger; Fig. 6 (b) and (c) are better layouts. The actual position and posture of the loading platform can also be calculated accurately by both the displacement sensors in Fig. 6 (a) and the inner displacement sensor of a stand-alone MAFS.

V. CALCULATION METHOD WITH DISPLACEMENT SENSORS ON A SENSOR FRAME

Fig. 7. Relationship of the coordinate systems between a displacement sensor and a stand-alone MAFS

Assuming that the initial position and posture of all of the sensors are calibrated accurately, as is shown in Fig. 7, K MAFSs are used in the distributed system. L displacement sensors are used to measure the position and posture of one MAFS. The generalized displacement of the k th MAFS in the local coordinate system, $o_k X_k Y_k Z_k$ is ${}^k \Delta^k$, while the generalized displacement of the (k, l) th displacement sensor in the local coordinate system $o_{k,l} X_{k,l} Y_{k,l} Z_{k,l}$ is ${}^{k,l} \Delta^{k,l}$ and the relationship between ${}^k \Delta^k$ and ${}^{k,l} \Delta^{k,l}$ is,

$$T_{o_k}^{k,l} {}^k \Delta^k = {}^{k,l} \Delta^{k,l}. \quad (3)$$

Where $T_{o_k}^{k,l}$ indicates the space vector transformation matrix from the coordinate system $o_k X_k Y_k Z_k$ to $o_{k,l} X_{k,l} Y_{k,l} Z_{k,l}$.

Fig. 9. Displacement of the aircraft supporting a wind loading

As is shown Fig. 9, the calculated global loading force is based on the global coordinate system fixed on the sensor frame. If we want the loading force to be based on the coordinate system fixed on the aircraft, the aircraft's displacement should be measured. A stereoscopic vision system is used to measure the displacement of the aircraft, as is shown in Fig. 9. All of the cameras are far from the MAFSSs (or simply fixed on the sensor frame). Then, the loading force in the coordinate system $o'x'y'z'$ can be calculated.

$${}^g_o Q' = T_g^{g'} {}^g_o Q \quad (10)$$

Where $T_g^{g'}$ indicates the transformation matrix from the coordinate $oxyz$ to $o'x'y'z'$.

Fig. 10. Typical automobile wind tunnel balance using a DMAFSS

Fig. 11. Typical thrust balance in thrust stands

A wind tunnel balance for an automobile is shown in Fig. 10, while some distributed thrust force-sensing systems are shown in Fig. 11.

VII. STAND-ALONE DISTRIBUTED MULTI-AXIS FORCE SENSOR

Fig. 12. Stand-alone distributed multi-axis force sensor

The sensor frame previously illustrated is fixed on the ground. If a stand-alone DMAFSS is needed, the sensor frame should be fixed on the supporting frame or the loading frame with an isolation structure (damping block), as shown in Fig. 12. Usually, the deformation of the loading frame is sharper than that of the supporting platform, and so if possible, the sensor frame is better fixed on the supporting frame.

Fig. 13. Deformation of a stand-alone multi-axis force sensor supporting a loading force

The global coordinate system of a distributed multi-axis force sensor (DMAFSS) is fixed on the sensor frame as shown in Fig. 13. It indicates that the global coordinate system is displaced with the sensor frame.

Because the entire DMAFSS moves in the space, the sensor frame is deformed by its inertial force. In addition, the measured force is influenced by the inertial force of the loading object, loading frame and loading platform. Therefore, the inertial force must be considered carefully in practical applications.

Fig. 14. Layout of displacement sensors on the sensor frame

Various DMAFSs are shown in Fig. 14. The deformation zone of a sensor frame should be sufficiently large to make the rest zone of the sensor frame a pseudo rigid zone. As is shown in Fig. 14 (e) and (f), either the upper or lower platform can be a suitable loading platform supporting an impact loading force with a large loading offset.

Fig. 15. Stewart-type MAFS and redundant-parallel-beam MAFS

The structures in Fig. 14 (e) and (f) is similar to that in Fig. 15 (a) and (b). The structures in Fig. 15 (a) and (b) can be regarded as a Stewart-type MAFS or redundant-parallel-beam MAFS. However, even the sensor frame can also be used to unify all of the forces into one coordinate system, with the deformation of both the loading and supporting frames affecting the measurement of beam forces profoundly, as shown in Fig. 15 (a) and (b). On the contrary, each branch is a stand-alone MAFS, as shown in Fig. 14 (e) and (f), and therefore the deformation of both the loading and supporting frames has almost no influence on the measurement accuracy of such a stand-alone MAFS. Moreover, the strain gauges can be fixed on the strain beams, as shown in Fig. 15 (c). Then, one single beam can be regarded as a stand-alone MAFS, as illustrated in [3, 27]. However, the measurement using the displacement sensor on the sensor frame is relatively complex, because no suitable pseudo rigid zone exists on such a single-beam MAFS.

Fig. 16. Distributed pseudo concentrated force and pseudo rigid sensor frame

In other words, as is shown in Fig. 16, although the deformation of the loading frame is large, if all the actual multi-axis pseudo-point-concentrated forces, q_i , can be measured accurately in their local coordinate systems by multiple stand-alone MAFSs, and all the forces can be accurately unified into one coordinate system by a pseudo-rigid sensor frame; the loading force, Q , can then be calculated accurately.

As to what is outlined above, both the mechanical hinge and flexure hinge can be used as shown in Fig. 16. The selection of the hinge type is dependent on the analysis of the loading capacity and loading offset, and this should be studied further.

VIII. CONCLUSION

A DMAFSS is introduced in this paper. An individual MAFS with a pseudo-point-concentrated-force can be regarded as a precise sensor. However, the loading capacity is minimal. The distributed system can increase the loading capacity. A pseudo-rigid sensor frame is vital for such a distributed system to unify the distributed forces into one coordinate system.

A deformation-harmonizing equations system and a displacement-solving equations system of MAFSs are proposed to calculate the practical position and posture parameters of a stand-alone MAFS for the forces unification.

Fig. 17. Distributed multi-axis force sensor on a manipulator

A large force-control manipulator is shown in Fig.17 (a). If a stand-alone MAFS is used to measure the force as shown in Fig.17 (b), the size of the structure is very large, and the accuracy is low. A DMAFSS can be applied in such a manipulator as shown in Fig.17 (c)~(e). A stereoscopic vision system can be fixed on the sensor frame to measure markers on the ground for the relationship determination between the sensor frame coordinate system and the ground coordinate system as shown in Fig.17 (f). The stereoscopic vision system can also be fixed on the ground along with multiple markers fixed on the sensor frame.

Fig. 18. Distributed multi-axis force sensor on motion stages

Similar DMAFSS can be applied in a parallel mechanism and a travelling crane as shown in Fig. 18.

Fig. 19. Application of a MAFS on an industrial manipulator

An industrial manipulator with a MAFS can be a simple force-feedback arm as shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** The force accuracy is relatively higher and the influence of inertial forces on the measurements is relatively smaller.

IX. SUMMARY OF PART ONE

Fig. 20. Relationship of the four papers

Part one of this series is the “Principle foundation” of the redundant parallel beam multi-axis force sensor. It includes four papers: (1) Multi-beam structure; (2) Observable variable; (3) Loading offset; and (4) Distributed sensing system. It is shown in part one that a highly accurate multi-axis force-sensing system can be realized by multiple pseudo-point-concentrated multi-axis sensors and a pseudo-rigid sensor frame.

As is shown in Fig. 20 (0), an elastic half-space supporting a point-concentrated force can be regarded as a linear elastic structure. If a distributed force is imposed on a rigid zone, the elastic half-space can also be regarded as a linear elastic structure. However, highly accurate observable variables can hardly be obtained in such a structure.

As is shown in Fig. 20 (1), papers 1 illustrates that if the loading and supporting platforms are rigid bodies or the generalized force is a point-concentrated force, whether a planar or three-dimensional redundant-parallel-beam structure can be regarded as a linear elastic structure in accordance with

Euler beam theory. Highly accurate observable variables can be obtained by strain gages affixed on the strain beams.

As is shown in Fig. 20 (2), paper 2 illustrates that various highly accurate observable variables can be obtained using the space vector transformation method and precision measurement principle. A displacement-solving equation system is derived using the space vector transformation. Various decoupling, highly precise and sensitive sensors/components can be applied to obtain the observable variables according to the displacement-solving equations system in accordance with the precision measurement principle.

As is shown in Fig. 20 (3), paper 3 illustrates that because the loading platform cannot be a rigid body and the loading force cannot be concentrated in a fixed point, the redundant-parallel-beam structure is not an accurate linear elastic structure; however, if the loading offset is sufficiently small or the size of the loading platform sufficiently large or the strain beam is sufficiently soft, the structure is sufficiently close to being linear elastic. Indeed, the loading capacity (especially the torque capacity) of such a structure is minimal.

As is shown in Fig. 20 (4), paper 4 illustrates that a distributed force-sensing system can profoundly enlarge the loading capacity and decrease the influence of the loading offset to the accuracy. A pseudo-rigid sensor frame is vital for unifying all of the distributed forces into one coordinate system and to calculate the generalized force of the distributed force-sensing system.

The characteristics of the principle of the redundant-parallel-beam multi-axis force sensor can be described as follows:

1. Based on the principles of Euler beam and space vector transformation, a redundant-parallel-beam structure supporting a point concentrate force can be regarded as a linear elastic system;

2. Based on the theories of precision measurement and space vector transformation, a highly precise observable variable can be obtained for the linear elastic system;

3. Based on the theory of elastic half-space, a sufficiently small loading neck and sufficiently large loading platform can make the redundant-parallel-beam structure a sufficiently accurate linear elastic structure;

4. Based on all of the above-mentioned principles and theories, a pseudo-rigid sensor frame can be used to unify all of the pseudo-point-concentrated forces into one coordinate system;

5. Both the local point-concentrated force of a stand-alone MAFS and the position and posture of the point-concentrated force can be solved by linear equations systems; the global force can be directly calculated by an explicit equations system.

In a practical design of a multi-axis force sensor / (sensing system), the sensor accuracy, loading capacity and outer loading force distributed state should be considered overall. All of the layout of the distributed structure, the size of the loading platform, the structure of the beam, the selection of the displacement sensor, the materials used in the structure, the inertial force of the loading frame and the deformation of the sensor frame by its inertial force should be designed according to the overall parameters. The measuring range, the calibration method are important for such a MAFS. All of these, mentioned above, should be further studied.

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